

ISARIC Anti-Stigma Guidelines: Annexes

Table of Contents

Annex 1: Systematic Review	2
Methods	2
Results	4
Annex 2: Supporting literature	9
Methods	9
Results	9
Annex 3: Stakeholder interviews	21
Methods	21
Results	21
Annex 4: Affected communities survey	24
Methods	24
Results	24
Annex 5: Evidence synthesis	27
Methods	27
Results	30
Annex 6: Expert consultation	74
Methods	74
Results	77
Annex 7: Contributors and declarations of interest	79
References	81

Annex 1: Systematic Review

Methods

We conducted a systematic review of primary studies to identify stigma reduction interventions supported by empirical evidence in the context of infectious disease outbreaks. We defined an outbreak as a rapid, unexpected increase in disease case numbers. Therefore, studies exploring stigma associated with endemic, chronic diseases, such as HIV and tuberculosis, were outside the scope of this review. The protocol for the systematic review has been registered and can be viewed on the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) (reference CRD420251007553).¹

PICO review question

- How effective are different stigma reduction interventions at minimising stigma for populations affected by infectious disease outbreaks when compared to no intervention or alternative interventions?

Eligibility criteria and search strategy

Eligibility criteria for studies included in the review are summarised in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Eligibility criteria for study inclusion in systematic review

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	Studies that include participants of any age, gender, or geographic location who are affected by, endorse, enact, or are positioned to influence stigma associated with an infectious disease outbreak. These may be individuals with or without personal experience of the disease.	Studies focused on non-outbreak disease contexts. Studies focused on marginalised groups being stigmatised during the time period of an outbreak but not due to association with the disease.
Intervention	Studies that describe the implementation of at least one intervention (including adaptations to policies and procedures) intended to reduce stigma associated with an outbreak-prone infectious disease.	Studies that describe general stigma reduction measures not applied to the context of infectious disease outbreaks.

Comparison	Studies that include a description of the evaluation of the interventions in comparison to routine practice, alternative interventions, or no intervention.	Studies without clear evaluation of effectiveness of interventions.
Outcome	Studies that report the effectiveness of interventions in reducing any form of outbreak-related stigma or improving social acceptance.	Studies that do not provide relevant data on intervention impact on stigma.
Study design	Peer-reviewed studies with comparative/evaluative design including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Randomised controlled trials - Quasi-experimental studies - Observational studies with comparative design - Mixed-methods studies - Qualitative studies 	Studies without a comparative or evaluative component; studies relying solely on conceptual discussions or theoretical models; protocols, guidelines, book sections, case reports, opinion pieces (editorials, viewpoints, commentaries); conference abstracts; preprints and other non-peer-reviewed literature.

Study screening selection and data extraction

Search terms for the key components ‘stigma’ or ‘social acceptance’ and ‘infectious disease outbreaks’ were combined using Boolean operators to search keyword fields and indexed subject headings. The search was not restricted by publication date or language. To establish a list of infectious disease outbreaks to explicitly include in the search strategy the following lists were reviewed: the World Health Organization (WHO) list of priority diseases, the UK government’s list of High Consequence Infectious Diseases, the WHO outbreak news reports, and the Centre for Disease Control (CDC)’s list of international outbreaks. Any disease that occurred on more than one list was included in the search terms.

Stigma-related terms included:

(stigma* OR prejudic* OR (discriminat* NOT ((discriminat* ADJ power) OR (discriminat* ADJ abilit*))) OR shame OR embarrass* OR humiliat* OR disapprov* OR (social* ADJ exclu*) OR (community ADJ exclu*) OR (social* ADJ reject*) OR (community ADJ reject*) OR marginali* OR ostraci* OR (social* ADJ accept*) OR (community ADJ accept*) OR (self ADJ accept*) OR (social* ADJ inclusi*) OR (community ADJ inclusi*) OR (social* ADJ approv*) OR (community ADJ approv*) OR reintegrat* OR (self ADJ worth) OR (self ADJ esteem) OR (self ADJ confidence)) along with related indexed terms (database dependent)

Outbreak-related terms included:

((infectious ADJ disease*) OR outbreak* OR epidemic* OR pandemic* OR (emerging ADJ disease*) OR (emerging ADJ infect*) OR (priority ADJ pathogen*) OR COVID-19 OR Coronavirus OR SARS* OR (severe ADJ acute ADJ respiratory ADJ syndrome) OR (Middle ADJ East ADJ respiratory ADJ syndrome) OR MERS-CoV OR (avian ADJ influenza*) OR (bird ADJ flu) OR H5N1 OR H7N9 OR H7N7 OR H5N6 OR Zika OR Ebola OR ebolavirus OR (Sudan ADJ virus) OR (haemorrhagic ADJ fever*) OR (hemorrhagic ADJ fever*) OR Marburg OR CCHF OR Nipah OR henipavir* OR (Lassa ADJ fever) OR Dengue OR (Rift ADJ Valley ADJ fever) OR mpox OR monkeypox OR measles OR plague OR (Yersinia ADJ pestis) OR oropouche) along with related indexed terms (database dependent).

All citations retrieved from the search described were uploaded to Rayyan systematic review software and deduplicated. Study screening and data extraction were conducted by three reviewers, with independent double screening and consensus meetings after every 10% of records until an 'excellent' level of inter-rater agreement was achieved ($\kappa > 0.75$).² Full-text articles were sourced for all citations included during the initial screening process. Those that could not be sourced were excluded. Eligible full texts were screened using the same process as the initial screening.

Quality assessment

Risk of bias was assessed using the revised Cochrane risk of bias tool (RoB 2) for randomised control trials (RCTs),³ the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Intervention Version 2 (ROBINS-I V2) for observational studies⁴ and the Critical Skills Appraisal Programme (CASP) Qualitative Studies Checklist for qualitative studies.⁵

Certainty of evidence

The GRADE⁶ (quantitative) and GRADE-CERqual⁷ (qualitative) frameworks were used to assess the certainty of the body of evidence identified from the systematic review. These were applied to each type of intervention identified in the review for the outcome of stigma reduction. The decision for each intervention is included in the evidence profiles in *Annex 5*.

Results

Results

The search identified 4,148 unique records; of which 76 were retrieved for full-text review, and 10 met the inclusion criteria (**Figure 1**). An additional 15 potentially relevant full texts were retrieved based on reference searching, with one meeting the inclusion criteria. In total, 11 studies describing and evaluating interventions to address stigma in the context of infectious disease outbreaks were included in the review.

Characteristics of included studies

The included studies were conducted between 2008 and 2024 across seven countries and comprised randomised controlled trials (n = 7) and qualitative studies (n = 4). The interventions addressed stigma related to COVID-19 (n = 6), Ebola disease (n = 2), mpox (n = 1), SARS (n = 1) and one hypothetical infectious disease scenario. Studies were implemented during both outbreak response (n = 7) and recovery (n = 4) phases.

Quality assessment

Risk-of-bias assessment indicated that most randomised controlled trials (n = 5) had “some concerns”, with one study assessed as high risk and one as low risk. All qualitative studies (n = 4) were judged to be methodologically robust overall.

Figure 1: Prisma flow diagram summarising study identification, screening and selection.

Source: Page MJ, et al.. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

Table 2: Characteristics of included studies: Systematic Review

First author, year	Study design	Country	Disease	Outbreak phase	Population	Sample size	Intervention	Outcome; Risk of bias assessment
Biesty, 2024 ⁸	Qualitative	UK	Mpox	Response	Priority populations disproportionately affected by mpox	11 (key informant interviews); 15 (workshops)	Community-led, LGBTQ+ organisation driven campaign to promote mpox vaccination and reduce stigma.	Mixed results; mostly methodologically sound*
Collier, 2023 ⁹	Qualitative	Sierra Leone	Ebola	Recovery	Recovered persons, affected families/ caregivers, community leaders	134 (focus group discussions)	Community-led Ebola sensitisation campaign, leveraging survivors, local leaders, and health workers to disseminate trusted information and reduce stigma.	Reduced stigma; mostly methodologically sound*
Crea, 2022 ¹⁰	Qualitative	Sierra Leone	Ebola	Recovery	Recovered persons, affected families/caregivers, community leaders	42 (key informant interviews), 187 (focus group discussions), 228 (total)	Community protection bylaws and education efforts by community leaders, healthcare workers and NGO workers.	Mixed results; mostly methodologically sound*

Islam, 2021 ¹¹	RCT	India	COVID-19	Response	Adults	1081 (intervention); 1057 (control)	Phone-based delivery of accurate COVID-19 information and anti-stigma messaging.	Reduced stigma; some concerns for bias†
Lu, 2021 ¹²	RCT	China	COVID-19	Response	College students returning from Wuhan to provinces outside Hubei Province	31 (intervention); 32 (control)	Brief, online reading and writing based psychological exercise.	Reduced stigma; some concerns for bias†
Siu, 2008 ¹³	Qualitative	Hong Kong	SARS	Recovery	Recovered persons	170 (observation and informal discussion); 30 (observation and in-depth interview)	Special clinics for SARS survivors with separate entrances and elevators.	Increased stigma; mostly methodologically sound*
Smith, 2012 ¹⁴	RCT	USA	Disease X	Response	Undergraduate students	333 (distributed across 16 experimental conditions)	Exposure to different stigma-inducing message components (e.g., labels, marks, transmission mode, and peril level) in a hypothetical infectious disease alert.	Increased stigma (high-peril messaging); some concerns for bias†
Techapoonpon, 2023 ¹⁵	RCT	Thailand	COVID-19	Recovery	Recovered persons for discharge from hospital	71 (intervention); 71 (control)	Brief, self-directed online mental health program.	Reduced stigma; some concerns for bias†

Tidwell, 2024 ¹⁶	RCT	Kenya	COVID-19	Response	Residents of informal settlements from households with adolescents	515 (intervention 1); 516 (intervention 2); 494 (control)	Brief, behaviourally framed text messages emphasising 1) reciprocity and 2) community support.	No change; some concerns for bias†
Valeri, 2021 ¹⁷	RCT	USA	COVID-19	Response	Adults	250 (control); 243 (intervention 1); 249 (intervention 2); 246 (intervention 3)	1) COVID-19 information sheet, 2) informational sheet plus a video encouraging digital social activity and 3) informational sheet plus a video sensitising viewers to COVID-19-related stigma.	Reduced stigma (interventions 2 & 3); high risk of bias†
Wang, 2024 ¹⁸	RCT	China	COVID-19	Response	Male adults	70 (within-sample, before and after comparison)	24IU intranasal oxytocin.	No change; low risk of bias†

*Adjudicated using CASP qualitative studies checklist.

†Adjudicated using the Cochrane revised risk of bias for RCTs tool (RoB 2)

‡ Adjudicated using the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies of Intervention Version 2 tool (ROBINS-I V2).

Abbreviations: IU – international units, NGO – non-governmental organisation, RCT – randomised controlled trial, SARS – severe acute respiratory syndrome, UK – United Kingdom, USA – United States of America

Annex 2: Supporting literature

Methods

We supplemented the systematic review with transferable findings from reviews of stigma reduction efforts in the context of other, established communicable diseases such as HIV, tuberculosis, and leprosy. To facilitate this, we tagged all relevant reviews during the screening stage of our own systematic review, manually screened reference lists of these reviews, and searched PROSPERO for additional completed reviews. We prioritised the inclusion of meta-reviews (i.e. reviews of systematic reviews), where available, and excluded individual reviews already covered within their scope to avoid duplication. We also invited the expert panel to propose any additional relevant reviews.

We extracted key transferable findings from each included review and assessed methodological quality using the AMSTAR 2 (Assessing the Methodological Quality of Systematic Reviews) checklist. The checklist was adapted to exclude Criterion 7 (listing all excluded studies) from the critical domains, due to feasibility constraints associated with reviews involving a high volume of exclusions. This aligns with the AMSTAR 2 guidance, which allows flexibility in assessing non-critical domains based on review context¹⁹.

We also considered qualitative or observational studies that, while not evaluating a specific intervention, offered insights relevant to the development or delivery of stigma reduction strategies. These were identified by tagging non-interventional studies excluded during screening but judged contextually relevant, and then reviewing this tagged set. The expert panel were again able to propose additional studies that may have been missed.

In parallel, we conducted a focused grey literature search to identify practical guidance and reports on stigma reduction in outbreak contexts. This involved site-specific queries on WHO, IFRC, MSF, UNICEF, Save the Children, and the Social Science in Humanitarian Action Platform (SSHAP) websites and community organisation websites suggested by two community co-investigators between 2nd and 15th of April 2025, as well as reference screening. Grey literature was considered independently at this stage rather than integrated into the systematic review since the review's eligibility criteria required studies to be externally peer-reviewed for quality purposes.

Results

We identified 15 indirectly relevant systematic reviews (two of which were meta-reviews). These reviews summarised interventions used to address stigma related to HIV (n=12), tuberculosis (n=6), leprosy (n=5), hepatitis B and C (n=1), filariasis (n=3), and other chronic neglected tropical diseases (n=1) (**Table 3A**). Most focused on the effectiveness of interventions (n=10), three reviewed acceptability, two reviewed prioritisation, and adoption,

appropriateness, feasibility, fidelity, cost, penetration, sustainability, value, and mechanisms were only explored in one review each.

We also included seven non-interventional primary studies that did not meet the systematic review eligibility criteria but provided data on the acceptability, prioritisation, societal implications, or implementation considerations of stigma reduction measures (**Table 3B**).

We found 27 relevant grey literature documents through our targeted search, including 17 from organisational websites (from a total of 714 results) and 10 through reference screening. None included any formal evaluation of the stigma reduction measures they described.

Table 3. Characteristics of included studies: Supporting literature

A. Indirectly relevant systematic reviews in established infectious disease contexts

First author, year	Country/Region	Infectious disease scope	Population	Review focus	Included studies	Included study designs	Intervention(s)	Outcome(s) of interest/Findings	AMSTAR 2
Anindhita, 2024 ²⁰	Africa, Asia, South America	HIV, leprosy, TB	People with the disease/household members in LMIC/high-burden countries	Effectiveness and mechanisms	30 studies	Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed methods	Community-based psychosocial support delivered by trained peer and lay providers	Reduction in internalised, enacted, anticipated and self-stigma	Moderate
Chang, 2014 ²¹	Africa, Europe, North America, South America, Asia	TB	People with or suspected of having the disease, relatives, community members and leaders, HCWs, NGO representatives	Description of stigma exacerbating factors	83 studies	Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed methods	NA	Restrictive public health practices and negative healthcare worker attitude towards the disease exacerbate stigma	Low

Driedger, 2018 ²²	Host: Western Europe and USA Origin: South America, Africa, South-East Asia, Middle East	HIV, TB, Hepatitis B and C virus	Migrant and forcibly displaced populations residing in HIC	Acceptability, accessibility and value	11 studies	Qualitative	Prevention, screening and treatment interventions for infectious diseases	Poorly culturally tailored, fear inducing interventions exacerbate stigma	Moderate
Feyissa, 2015 ²³	Sub-Saharan Africa	HIV	People with the disease	Effectiveness	9 studies	Quantitative (Experimental, observational)	Home based HIV counselling and testing	Reduction in perceived and enacted stigma	Moderate
Gronholm, 2021 ²⁴	North America, South America, Africa, Asia	HIV, leprosy, TB	People with the disease, general public, HCWs, caregivers	Effectiveness, prioritisation, value	6 systematic reviews	Systematic reviews	Group-based behavioural interventions, community support initiatives, patient-centred mental health programmes, information sharing to community leaders and	Reduction in enacted, anticipated, internalised and self-stigma	High

							peers, structural support to access care		
Hartog, 2020 ²⁵	Africa, South-East Asia	HIV, filariasis, leprosy, TB	Children and adolescents	Effectiveness	61 studies	Quantitative, qualitative	Community education, individual empowerment, social contact	Reduction in stigma	Low
Hofstraat, 2016 ²⁶	Africa, Asia, North America, South America, Europe	Neglected tropical diseases	People with the disease, community members	Effectiveness	52 studies	Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed methods	Stigma targeted health education, integrated psychosocial support, community contact	Reduced community, internalised, anticipated and experienced stigma	Low
Kemp, 2019 ²⁷	Africa, Asia, Middle East, South America, Europe, Caribbean	HIV, filariasis, leprosy, TB	Adults and children with the disease or in the community	Review of the use of implementation science	35 studies	Quantitative, Qualitative	School-based peer education programme, comic book aimed to reduce stigma for school children, stigma reduction programmes, information	Reduction in community, experienced, internalised and anticipated stigma	Moderate

							sharing/education		
Layland, 2020 ²⁸	Africa, Asia, North America, Australia/New Zealand	HIV	Sexual and gender minorities (SGM) with or at risk of the disease	Review of interventions targeting SGM with or at risk of HIV	40 studies	Quantitative	Intersectional interventions that target both SGM status and health status	Lack of intersectional interventions or effect, but stigma reduction effect for some interventions	Low
Majeed, 2024 ²⁹	Africa, Western Pacific	HIV	Health professionals, general public, children/adolescents, people with the disease, caregivers, students, community leaders, researchers, teachers	Effectiveness	192 studies	Quantitative	Educational interventions, social contact, increased access to services, counselling/mentoring, social activism	Mostly positive reduction in stigma, but no association between nature of intervention and change in stigma outcomes	Low

Nyblade, 2019 ³⁰	North America, South America, Asia, Africa	HIV	People with the disease, HCWs	Descriptive and Effectiveness	37 studies	Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed Methods	Workshops for HCWs (lecture, discussion, role-play) including ones that are PLHIV-led (with testimony), training hospital champions of stigma reduction, integration of HIV care into primary services	Mixed effect or reduction in stigma attitudes, knowledge, fear	Moderate
Rao, 2019 ³¹	North America, Asia, Africa, Middle East, Australia	HIV, leprosy	People with the disease, community, caregivers, healthcare workers	Effectiveness	24 studies	Quantitative	Education, contact, coping skills acquisition, social support, drama, problem solving	Mixed results in stigma reduction	Low
Sengupta, 2011 ³²	North America, Europe, Asia, Africa	HIV	Students, healthcare providers, community,	Effectiveness	19 studies	Quantitative	Information sharing, skill-building, counselling and	Reduction in stigmatising attitudes	Moderate

			families, women				testimony from PLHIV		
Stangl, 2013 ³³	North America, Middle East, Africa, Asia, South America, Australia, Caribbean	HIV	Students/ youth, caregivers, healthcare workers, people with/at risk of the disease, community	Effective ness, acceptabi lity, prioritisa tion	48 studies	Quantitative , Qualitative	Information sharing, skills building, contact, counselling and support, structural changes, biomedical changes (e.g. introduction of ART)	Mixed results (mostly reduction in stigma)	Moderat e
Stangl, 2023 ³⁴	North America, South America, Asia, Africa	HIV	People with the disease (women, health workers, ethnic minorities, SGM, immigrants)	Effective ness, inter- sectionali ty	23 studies	Quantitative	Multistrategy (information, skills building, counseling support, contact, structural, biomedical, expressive writing)	Mixed results (half reduction in stigma)	Moderat e

B. Non-interventional primary studies

First author, year	Study design	Country/Region	Disease scope	Outbreak phase	Population	Sample size	Study Focus	Transferable learnings	CASP
Fagnoli, 2021 ³⁵	Qualitative with questionnaire	Switzerland	COVID-19	Response	Members of public, public health decision makers	11 FGD, 14 interviews	Acceptability of disease immunity certificates	Not accepted, potentially harmful	Mostly methodologically sound
Ford, 2021 ³⁶	Rapid environmental scan	USA	COVID-19	Preparedness/Response	NA	NA	Adequacy of existing surveillance systems to monitor racism, social stigma and inequities	Existing systems do not adequately capture real-time data	NA
Kwon, 2022 ³⁷	Observational	USA	COVID-19	Response	Adults	8 386 survey respondents	Impact of mask mandates on stigma and social attitudes	Mixed results; mask wearers stigmatised before mandates, with reversal after mandates introduced	Serious concerns
Lamb, 2018 ³⁸	Qualitative	West Africa	Ebola	Response	UK Armed Forces	14 interviews	Factors affecting delivery of healthcare on a	Pre-deployment training generated competence,	Mostly methodologically

					medical personnel		humanitarian operation	confidence and understanding	y sound
Musoke, 2025 ³⁹	Qualitative	Uganda	Ebola	Response	Community members, community health workers; governmental, NGO and community leadership	25 FGD, 32 interviews	Barriers to community engagement in intervention design and implementation	Delayed consultation, poor communication and misinformation, limited HR support, institutional and coordination challenges	Mostly methodologically sound
Nyarko, 2015 ⁴⁰	Qualitative	Ghana	Ebola	Preparedness	Multidisciplinary health professionals	15 members of a roundtable discussion	Health professionals perspectives on preparing for disease onset	Co-create anti-stigma educational messaging with key community groups	Mostly methodologically sound
Parveen 2016 ⁴¹	Qualitative	Bangladesh	Nipah	Preparedness, Response	Community members, religious leaders, caregivers	10 informal discussions, 11 interviews, 4 FGD, community	Community residents explanations for disease transmission and reasons for	Use culturally tailored two-way communication, e.g. an image-based dialogue session	Mostly methodologically sound

						group meetings	misunderstanding		
Person, 2004 ⁴²	Qualitative (with rapid situational assessment)	USA	SARS	Response	Asian American community leaders, other stakeholders	70 people in group discussions	Understand and develop strategies to target SARS fear and stigma in the Asian community	Develop simple, tailored prevention messaging, Asian-language information materials, multiple varying channels of dissemination, establish community partnerships for education, ensure the CDC provides continued leadership	Mostly methodologically sound
Zalwango, 2024 ⁴³	Qualitative	Uganda	Ebola	Response	Ebola survivors, household members, district	30 interviews	Experiences of stigma	Community and self isolation and rejection, loss of work, banning from community and	Mostly methodologically sound

officials/
HCWs

educational
spaces; stigma
was worsened
by receiving
HCW attention

ART, Antiretroviral therapy; **CASP**, Critical Appraisal Skills Programme; **FGD**, focus group discussion; **HCW**, healthcare worker; **HIC**, high income country; **HIV**, human immunodeficiency virus; **HR**, human resources; **LMIC**, low-middle income country; **NA**, not applicable; **NGO**, non-governmental organisation; **PLHIV**, people living with HIV; **SARS**, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome; **SGM**, sexual and gender minority; **TB**, tuberculosis; **UK**, United Kingdom; **USA**, United States of America

Annex 3: Stakeholder interviews

Methods

We thematically analysed 37 in-depth stakeholder interviews conducted in an earlier phase of this project to assess stakeholder support, perceived feasibility, and prioritisation of recommendations and to capture suggestions that may lack an empirical evidence base. We employed maximum variation purposive sampling to ensure representation of all WHO regions, relevant disciplines and outbreak-prone pathogen expertise (acknowledging that there would be an over-representation of COVID-19 and Ebola disease due to the number of stakeholders involved in these outbreaks). The primary manuscript from these interviews contains further methodological details⁴⁴.

Results

Stigma reduction suggestions were identified from the stakeholder interviews, and initially organised according to the phase of outbreak they were predominantly relevant to: preparedness, response, and recovery. Four major themes were inductively identified across these suggestions:

- Knowledge exchange: public health communication, education, and community engagement.
- Policy and service design: structural or operational adaptations, such as changes to infrastructure or procedures intended to reduce stigma or prevent its institutional reinforcement.
- Psychosocial support: psychological counselling, social services, or skill-building resources.
- Community involvement and advocacy: activism by or with people with lived experience of the illness and affected community organisations, aiming to shift social norms and promote equity.

Stakeholder suggestions are organised by outbreak phase and theme in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Stakeholder suggestions for reducing outbreak-related stigma

Theme	Preparedness	Response	Recovery
Knowledge exchange	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid disease names linked to places or animals. <p><i>"The viral memes that go around of pictures of like monkeys and this kind of idea of people having sex with them... you know, it's not funny to the people who are on the receiving end"</i> - Interview 8,</p>	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid fear-based messages. <p><i>"Stop using fear appeals as a communication technique during outbreaks. Don't do that. It perpetuates stigma. It is really harmful."</i> - Interview 4, Multi-outbreak social and behavioural scientist</p>	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide recovery information for employers/educators. <p><i>"Many times some people are just out of their jobs. They're not allowed to be given their jobs again, those that have been working... we can talk with them with the employers and ask them to be accepted back."</i> - Interview</p>

	<p>Community advocate and non-governmental mpox response coordinator</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support regular community dialogues in high-risk areas. • Provide anti-stigma responder training. • Train spokespeople to avoid criminalising, moralistic, or othering language. • Integrate stigma education into schools. 	<p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote two-way risk communication. • Embed anti-stigma messages in risk reduction. • Address emerging local rumours. • Centre messaging on transmission not identity. • Highlight solidarity, not division. 	<p>22, COVID-19 and Ebola mental health lead and Ministry of Health official</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid language that implies pity or defect when talking about recovery.
<p>Policy and service design</p>	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design facilities to optimise safe contact with loved ones and healthcare workers. <p><i>"Facilities should be designed such that they ease the access of health workers without them having donned protective clothing. And the same for the relatives."</i> - Interview 34, Multi-outbreak health facility manager</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build protocols that prioritise dignified, holistic care. • Involve social scientists in guideline review. • Improve trustworthiness of organisations. 	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treat personal items respectfully and allow for retention when possible. <p><i>"So they would throw away everything that belonged to you then. Only this very last outbreak, I saw that when you were discharged, they were thinking about returning gadgets, like phones."</i> - Interview 15, Ebola clinical responder and trainer</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protect privacy at health service sites and in communities. • Involve local leaders before law enforcement. • Allow visual confirmation after death. • Consider reassurance measures such as temperature screening. • Consider home-based quarantine 	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce visibility of follow-up services <p><i>"The survivors feel the follow up is enough based on the fact that the neighbours still wonder, are these people still sick? Were they returned when they are sick? Or why are they still following them?...So that stigma still goes on."</i> - Interview 25, COVID-19 and Ebola disease psychosocial team member</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate respectful contact between recovered individuals and outbreak responders.

<p>Psychosocial support</p>	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-plan psychosocial support programmes. <p><i>"I think that the whole question of human behaviour is just so fundamentally missed in a lot of outbreak responses, like we just start chasing pathogens rather than helping humans."</i> - Interview 16, Multi-outbreak international response coordinator and public health expert</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train and supervise psychosocial care providers adequately. 	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve support teams early. <p><i>"Psychosocial counseling has to be thought of immediately."</i> - Interview 27, Ebola disease and COVID-19 clinical responder and Ebola survivor programme lead</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support responder mental health. • Strengthen factors that foster social cohesion. • Provide resources at discharge if needed. 	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screen psychosocial wellbeing at follow-up. <p><i>These people suffered quite a lot... So I think [what is needed is] to start up some kind of a follow up program or clinic or survivor programme to follow up these people in regards to the psychosocial.</i> - Interview 27, Ebola disease and COVID-19 clinical responder and Ebola survivor programme lead</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate recovery celebrations. • Document and improve stigma reduction and support systems.
<p>Community involvement and advocacy</p>	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with communities to develop stigma assessment tools. <p><i>"There are currently no methods of assessing the effectiveness of [Ebola disease reintegration programmes] ... only anecdotes from the community of stigma reducing, but hopefully that will be in place in time for the next outbreak"</i> - Interview 14, COVID-19 and Ebola disease psychosocial lead and clinical responder</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage prior outbreak community advocates. • Include potentially affected groups in planning. 	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve survivors in community outreach roles. <p><i>"I don't think those who came later, like after me, experienced it like I did because by the time they came, I think the psychosocial team had used me, like taking me to the community. They showed people that I'm free. I shared my experience."</i> - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-design response measures and messages with communities. • Ensure communication is locally led. • Consult communities before rolling out new policies. • Centre lived experiences in media. 	<p>Illustrative example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support peer-led survivor groups. <p><i>"I created an association of survivors.... It is still moving and is still on ground fighting discrimination and stigma. We visit each other with these families that lost their relatives in the outbreak. We take care of the kids or orphans of the deceased as an association."</i> - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead</p> <p>Other suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve survivors in community outreach roles.

Annex 4: Affected communities survey

Methods

We have also incorporated results from a single question in a stigma survey we conducted across three outbreak settings to provide insights into community acceptability and prioritisation. The survey was anonymous and asked affected community members about Ebola stigma in Uganda, mpox stigma in the UK, and Nipah stigma in Bangladesh. Respondents included recovered persons, household members, response workers and other community members (non-representative quota sampling). The included question asked respondents to select measures they believed would reduce stigma from a list of commonly recommended stigma reduction interventions. They could additionally select 'Other' to write in their own suggestions. In the Nipah-specific survey this question was only asked to those with lived experience of the illness. *[We are happy to provide further details on survey methods to those interested; the related manuscript is currently under review and will hopefully be referenced here].*

Results

The survey included community members affected by Ebola from Uganda (N=302), by mpox in the UK (N=437) and those with lived experience of Nipah virus disease in Bangladesh (N=30). **Table 5**, below, shows the responses of community members in support of various stigma reduction measures.

Table 5. Community support for stigma reduction measures across Ebola (Uganda), Mpox (UK), and Nipah (Bangladesh) outbreaks.

Stigma reduction measure	No. respondents in support of measure (%)		
	Uganda (Ebola stigma), N = 302	UK (mpox stigma), N = 437	Bangladesh (Nipah stigma), N = 30*
More public education	290 (96)	392 (90)	28 (93)
More awareness campaigns about stigma	259 (86)	332 (76)	24 (80)
More thoughtful public health messages	244 (81)	302 (69)	22 (73)
Opportunities to hear the stories of people who have recovered	251 (83)	225 (51)	22 (73)
More psychological support	228 (75)	180 (41)	19 (63)
Recovery certificates	216 (72)	83 (19)	14 (47)

More laws to stop discrimination	148 (49)	159 (36)	8 (27)
Other	74 (25)	7 (2)	5 (17)
None of the above	0 (0)	15 (3)	5 (17)

**in Bangladesh only asked to those who had personal lived experience of Nipah virus disease*

A range of open-text suggestions were provided, predominantly by respondents in Uganda. These responses have been thematically grouped in **Table 6**. Where multiple respondents shared similar views, the responses were synthesized and the number of mentions noted. Unique responses have been included as direct quotes.

Table 6. Open text responses on stigma reduction interventions from community respondents

Theme	Uganda (Ebola)	UK (mpox)	Bangladesh (Nipah)
More community engagement with greater geographic reach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community dialogues supported instead of campaigns (4 respondents). • Health education must be continuous, even without outbreaks (2 respondents). • “We need meetings where community members can ask silly question.” • “More sensitisation for those far away from the cases, those close have got enough.” 	–	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Door-to-door awareness.”
Responsible communication through mass media and education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Health talks on radio and in schools...” • “Whenever community hear announcements on radio they say ah they’ve started their same things. If you print so many billboards the community attitude will not change. The reading culture is poor.” • “Should have a day gazetted for National Ebola celebration.” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Stopping sensationalist newspaper and online article headlines that encourage abhorrent behaviour to generate clicks.” • “More media education about mpox and any potential associations between certain diseases and certain groups to promote responsible reporting and less sensationalisation of news related to infectious disease”. 	–
Accurate and timely communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving close relatives, community and religious leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Trying to ensure the managers of the response share accurate information.” 	

n from governments and community leaders	<p>and key community members in the response (4 respondents)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Faster communication from the government.” • “Integrate into church sermons. Involve community and religious leaders.” 		
Evidence-based approaches to risk stratification	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Testing criteria should be based on actual risk and not on sexual orientation or gender identity.” 	-
Recovery and reintegration of survivors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support for survivors and family members who lost someone to Ebola (4 respondents). • “Even wives want recovery certificates” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Now that we are familiar with covid, I think we accept diseases and recovery a bit more as a society, maybe likening it to that experience of not being contagious after X amount of time.” 	-
Promotion of privacy of survivors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The ambulance would come make a big fuss—better to just take the person in a car.” • “Limit the number of health workers visiting survivors (rather call or ask survivor to attend the clinic).” 	-	-
Involvement of healthcare workers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good communication between health workers and community (4 respondents) • “Health workers will be more trusted than survivors.” • “Give healthcare workers enough [PPE] so they can properly touch and care for patients.” 	-	-
Involvement of survivors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survivors will be more trusted than health workers (2 respondents). • “Get people to meet ebola survivors then they will see they are the same.” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “As with HIV stigma, awareness of those in groups not deemed “high risk” or those that feel low-risk... actually someone physically saying ‘it happened to me’.” 	-

Annex 5: Evidence synthesis

Methods

The writing group used a structured multi-step approach to synthesise findings from the following sources:

- Systematic review of outbreak-specific interventions (*Annex 1*)
- Supporting literature from established infectious diseases and grey sources (*Annex 2*)
- Stakeholder interviews (*Annex 3*)
- Affected communities survey (*Annex 4*)

This process generated the guiding principles and recommended interventions, distinguishing between cross-cutting practices to prevent stigma and phase-specific actions to reduce it. The synthesis was conducted in four steps:

Step 1: Identification and classification

All possible stigma mitigation measures identified across the evidence base were extracted and reviewed. These included intervention strategies, response adaptations, value-based actions, and operational recommendations. Each was classified as either:

A guiding principle: a cross-cutting, value- or rights-based practice that is intended to prevent organisations contributing to the emergence or reinforcement of stigma.

A recommended intervention: a specific, evidence-informed action that can be implemented during a particular outbreak phase to actively reduce stigma.

Classification was based on scope, specificity, and basis for suggestion. Where the distinction was unclear, items were discussed by the core working group until agreement.

Step 2: Organising framework

The four thematic domains derived inductively from the stakeholder interviews were used to group principles and their associated good practice indicators, namely **communication and knowledge exchange**, **psychosocial support**, **policy and service design**, and **community involvement and advocacy**.

Recommended interventions were grouped according to the phase of the outbreak in which they were considered most relevant or actionable: **preparedness, response, or recovery**, to allow potential implementers to identify timely, context-specific actions based on the current phase of outbreak.

Step 3: Drafting and refinement

For each guiding principle, a rationale and set of good practice indicators were developed, informed by the source materials and relevant human rights frameworks.

For each recommended intervention, we developed a structured entry that included implementation notes and practical examples, types of stigma addressed, and a summary of the supporting evidence and WHO-INTEGRATE considerations.

All content was refined in an iterative process by the working group, including discussion during three half-day meetings.

Step 4: Application of the WHO-INTEGRATE framework

Each recommended intervention was appraised using the WHO-INTEGRATE framework⁴⁵. The sub-criteria applied, and the main sources of evidence drawn on for each, are detailed in **Table 7**. These include considerations related to effectiveness, equity, societal implications, human rights and acceptability, feasibility, and financial implications.

Table 7: WHO-INTEGRATE criteria, subcriteria, and sources of evidence used in evidence to recommendations process

WHO-INTEGRATE Criterion	Sub-criteria used	Sources of evidence
Balance of health benefits and harms	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Efficacy or effectiveness on health of individuals• Effectiveness or impact on health of population• Safety-risk-profile of intervention• Broader positive or negative health-related impacts	Systematic review findings (quantitative and qualitative), supplemented by indirect evidence from established infectious diseases.
Health equity, equality, and non-discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Distribution of benefits and harms• Accessibility of intervention• Impact on health equity	Systematic review findings, survey data, supplemented by indirect evidence from established infectious diseases, and stakeholder interviews.
Societal implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Social impact	Systematic review findings, survey data, supplemented by indirect evidence from established infectious diseases, and stakeholder interviews
Human rights and socio-cultural acceptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Accordance with universal human rights standards• Socio-cultural acceptability to patients/beneficiaries and implementers	Stakeholder interviews and survey data across three outbreak contexts, indirect systematic reviews and additional non-interventional literature.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio-cultural acceptability to the public and stakeholders • Impact on autonomy • Intrusiveness of intervention 	
Feasibility and health system considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership and governance • Interaction with and impact on health system • Need for and impact on workforce and human resources • Need for and impact on infrastructure 	Feasibility themes from stakeholder interviews, community surveys, and qualitative studies; indirect support from reviews describing health system constraints.
Financial and economic considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial impact • Ratio of costs and benefits 	Limited direct cost data; inferences based on feasibility discussions in stakeholder interviews and economic data from related reviews.
Meta-criterion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of evidence 	Based on GRADE and GRADE-CERQual assessments applied to the systematic review base, then adjusted according to appraisal of full body of supporting evidence using CERQual criteria (methodological limitations, coherence, adequacy, relevance).

These WHO-INTEGRATE criteria were initially scored by the writing and leadership groups using the following key with a justification provided for each then reviewed and adjusted by the expert panel:

Figure 2: WHO-INTEGRATE criteria scoring

Favours business as usual (negative)	Probably favours business as usual (probably negative)	Favours neither or uncertain	Probably favours intervention (probably positive)	Favours interventions (positive)
--------------------------------------	--	------------------------------	---	----------------------------------

The **overall quality of the evidence** supporting each intervention was initially based on the GRADE (for quantitative studies) or GRADE-CERQual (for qualitative studies) within the outbreak-specific systematic review, then adjusted across the full body of evidence using CERQual criteria: methodological limitations, coherence, adequacy, and relevance. The following quality of evidence scoring key is adopted in the results:

Figure 3: Quality of evidence scoring

Very low	Low	Moderate	High
----------	-----	----------	------

Results

The details of the guiding principles are fully captured in the primary document. This results section therefore focuses on providing the evidence-to-decision profiles for the recommended interventions.

Evidence and WHO-INTEGRATE profiles for recommended stigma reduction interventions

A) Recommended interventions to reduce stigma during outbreak preparedness:

Recommended Intervention A1
We recommend providing stigma-sensitive training to service providers who interact with affected individuals, including providers outside health settings.
Evidence profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
<p>Driedger M et al. 2018 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) includes one study (Tomas et al.. 2013) that reported that the presence of medical interpreters often resulted in reluctance to report TB symptoms due to confidentiality concerns²³.</p> <p>Nyblade L et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) and Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) report that a wide range of information-provision interventions and “skills-building activities” that helped healthcare providers develop the appropriate skills to work directly with the stigmatised group were effective in reducing chronic infectious disease stigma^{25,31}.</p> <p>The review by Gronholm et al. found that professionally assisted peer group interventions, modular interactive training, participatory self-guided assessment and intervention, contact strategy combined with information provision and empowerment can reduce stigma²⁵. The review by Nyblade et al. also found that interventions such as role-play, lectures, and participatory training of popular opinion leaders within different hospitals were effective in several settings (and often used in combination)³¹.</p> <p>One included study involving police officers (Krameddine YI et al. 2013 from Hanisch S et al. 2016 review) examined the effectiveness of role play training with highly trained actors and found it to be a cost-effective means to reduce directly measured negative behaviours, such as the use of force, although this was towards people with mental illness^{46,47}. Training costs amounted to approximately \$120 per officer and resulted in estimated savings of over \$80,000 within six months due to increased efficiency in handling mental health-related incidents and reduced use of force.</p> <p>Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) includes a study on a stigma reduction curriculum for nurses which was rated highly by the participants²⁸. A few nurses said materials made them uncomfortable (Shah SM et al. 2014)⁴⁸.</p>

Additional non-interventional studies		
Lamb D et al. 2018 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) Interviews with the first UK military medical personnel deployed during the Ebola outbreak in West Africa found that collective pre-deployment training fostered competence, confidence, and team cohesion ³⁸ .		
Stakeholder interviews illustrative quotes		
"And probably think about educating the police... maybe even the vets as well because the vets might not want to visit the farms and then people start to lose their livelihoods." - Interview 11, Multi-outbreak response coordinator and researcher		
"I thought it was just a knowledge gap on their side that [the healthcare workers] would stigmatise us... It called for a training, to have them trained and give them information about survivors so that next time they interact with them, they interact with them with confidence." - Interview 27, Ebola disease and COVID-19 clinical responder and Ebola survivor programme lead		
Affected communities survey		
In the Ugandan-cohort open-text responses four respondents suggested that improving communication between health workers and the community would reduce stigma. One respondent recommended 'healthcare worker training'. Another suggested that survivor stories should be focused towards healthcare workers rather than the general population.		
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment		
Health benefits/harm	The intervention lacks direct evidence of effectiveness for affected populations or society from our systematic reviews (indirect supporting evidence from established infectious disease systematic reviews). The intervention may be applicable to a wide range of conditions, potentially increasing net benefit.	
Probably favours intervention		
Health equity/non-discrimination		
Probably favours intervention		
Societal implications		
Probably favours intervention		
Human rights and acceptability		Stakeholder interviews and open text survey results supported the intervention. Intrusiveness is assessed as low.
Probably favours intervention		
Financial and economic considerations		The intervention is dependent on available educators, proactive leadership, and frontline worker time capacity. The intervention may be applicable to a wide range of conditions, potentially increasing cost-effectiveness. Data on cost-effectiveness was supportive but indirect and limited to police force mental health stigma training. Feasibility and financial considerations are expected to vary by outbreak setting.
Probably favours intervention		
Feasibility of integration		
Uncertain		

Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Drawn from stakeholder interviews, indirect evidence from moderate-high quality reviews of stigma related to other infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2), single context open-text survey results, and one additional methodologically sound (CASP) qualitative study on other benefits.
Low	

Recommended Intervention A2	
We recommend including stigma awareness as a component of health education initiatives for children and adolescents, particularly when an outbreak may affect these age groups.	
Evidence Profile	
Primary evidence from systematic review	
Very low certainty evidence (CERQUAL) from 1 x qualitative study (Collier KM, 2023), which included reports that a school principal encouraging support for those recovered from Ebola disease was believed to improve reintegration of affected children ⁹ .	
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews	
<p>Hartog K et al. 2020 (AMSTAR 2: Low) found that all child-focussed stigma reduction interventions for chronic health conditions reported positive results (n=13) and that most of these used educational techniques, with a predominance of interractional modalities²⁶. They note that children and adolescents are underrepresented in stigma reduction efforts in low- and middle-income countries and conclude that there is a need for more stigma reduction interventions in these regions that target a broader range of stigmas, with children as both direct and indirect target groups. They found that printed materials or films were usually used to deliver child-focused interventions while professionals were most often responsible for adult-focused interventions.</p> <p>Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) included a filariasis study in Egypt (el-Setouhy MA. Rio F. 2003) which found a comic book was an effective means of reducing schoolchildren avoiding affected classmates (p<0.001) and a youth-led HIV education program in Zambian schools, which was reported to cost US\$21 per beneficiary (Denison J et al. 2012, included in Kemp CG et al. 2019)^{28,49,50}. Another included study reports that 76.6% of students considered HIV school peer education programme beneficial; and reported that framing the programme as 'life skills', avoiding clashes with academic obligations, and support by school staff increased acceptability (Al-Iryani B et al. 2013)⁵¹.</p>	
Additional non-interventional studies	
N/A	
Stakeholder interviews	

"They need to reach out to schools. I must say that. During the outbreak, there was one student... he was negative two times, and when we took him back to the school, the whole school ran away from him. And that wasn't good. Including the teachers. So institutions of learning and others must not be left aside." - Interview 26, COVID-19 and Ebola disease clinical responder and mental health lead

Affected communities survey

In the Ugandan open-text survey responses four respondents suggested health talks at schools.

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	There is very low certainty evidence of effectiveness from a single qualitative study of stigma reduction education in schools improving reintegration, with indirect supporting evidence from established disease systematic reviews. Relationships developed with educators and school leadership may be helpful in future outbreak response. The intervention may be applicable to a wide range of conditions, increasing potential net benefit.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	
Uncertain	
Feasibility of integration	The intervention requires the development of materials and the mobilising of human resources which may be associated with some costs. Integration into existing education initiatives could minimise required human resources. There is indirect evidence from established systematic reviews of similar interventions being implemented successfully in low resource settings, but feasibility is likely to vary depending on the setting.
Probably favours intervention	
Overall quality of evidence	Very low certainty direct evidence of effectiveness (CERQUAL) from single qualitative study in the outbreak-related systematic review with additional indirect supporting evidence from two established disease systematic reviews of low to moderate quality (AMSTAR 2). Socio-cultural
Low	

	acceptability evidence came from stakeholder interviews and open text survey data in one setting. Very limited evidence of cost-effectiveness or feasibility. The cross-source coherence in the limited available evidence informed an overall low confidence rating.
--	---

Recommended Intervention A3
We recommend predesigning psychosocial support interventions that can be delivered under strict infection control measures.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
Moderate certainty evidence (GRADE) from 2 x RCTs (Techapoonpon K et al. 2023; Lu T et al, 2021) ^{13,16} . Techapoonpon et al. demonstrated that a brief online destigmatisation program in Thailand significantly reduced COVID-19-related stigma among survivors within two weeks post-discharge from hospital ¹⁶ . Lu et al. demonstrated that a brief reading-and-writing-based intervention significantly reduced perceived discrimination among Chinese college students returning home from Wuhan during COVID-19, by enhancing their perceived social support ¹³ .
Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) suggest that stigma (anticipated, enacted, and internalised) can be reduced through strategies building on group-based interventions, psycho-educational interventions, social empowerment strategies, community-based strategies and self-help interventions, and that family-based interventions and strategies based on empowerment are recommended to mitigate self-stigma (based on chronic infectious disease systematic review) ²⁵ . Sengupta S et al. 2011 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) found that counselling and skill-building were linked to reduced stigmatising attitudes among participants ³³ . Anindhita M et al. 2024 (AMSTAR 2 Moderate) found that community-based psychosocial support interventions, particularly those delivered by trained laypersons or peers, were found to reduce internalised, enacted, anticipated, and self-stigma among individuals affected by HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and leprosy ²¹ . The latter emphasised the need for adequate training for lay and recovered persons.
Additional non-interventional studies
N/A
Stakeholder interviews
"This time around, we didn't have to enter. We had, like a form of a radio... so someone could, you know, speak and you would clearly hear them and talk to them. They didn't have to enter. So somehow that worked very well." - Interview 22, COVID-19 and Ebola mental health lead and Ministry of Health official

"At the point where a pandemic happens, everyone's just rushing to get everything done. You can't actually just develop and plan these things in a day. But if you actually put in a lot of effort into planning these things or health security or health system strengthening kind of perspective, you know, um, this whole like, disease X mentality, right? I think, you would then not have to grapple with these things, when it happens." - Interview 32, Multi-outbreak public health practitioner and community advocate

Affected communities survey

75%, 63% and 41% of respondents supported the suggestion of more psychological support as a stigma reduction measure in Uganda (Ebola), Bangladesh (Nipah) and UK (mpox) respectively.

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	There is moderate certainty evidence that digitally administered psychosocial support aids are effective in reducing the stigma perceived by individuals in outbreak contexts. There is supporting evidence (including a large body of indirect evidence from established infectious diseases) for individual benefit, and desirable societal implications. From available data, these interventions appear to mostly be effective in the short term. The intervention may also be beneficial for other psychosocial concerns. The intervention would improve equitable access to mental healthcare.
Favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	
Uncertain	
Feasibility of integration	Interventions are anticipated to be low cost and feasible, with increased feasibility in settings with good access to digital platforms. Costs of staff would vary depending if implemented in-person or digitally and by lay persons or professionals.
Probably favours intervention	
Overall quality of evidence	Moderate certainty evidence from primary studies (GRADE) with triangulating
Moderate	

	supporting evidence from moderate-high quality indirectly relevant systematic reviews (AMSTAR 2), stakeholder interviews, and surveys across three contexts.
--	--

Recommended Intervention A4
We suggest facilitating community dialogues about relevant infectious diseases and stigma in outbreak-prone areas as part of outbreak preparedness.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
Hofstraat K et al. 2016 (AMSTAR 2: Low) , in their systematic review of social stigma in neglected tropical diseases, concluded that health education interventions are useful to reduce community stigma but noted that to be effective, health education needs to address specific cultural and religious beliefs, and the specific questions and fears that people have in a given community, and needs to be combined with other interventions ²⁷ . Rao D et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Low) found that most studies used educational approaches and reported statistically significant declines in at least one measure of stigma but only a few reported measures of practical significance ³² . Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) summarises a study of lay healthcare educator delivered podocooniosis education and rumour-busting sessions and found various weaknesses including that some educators provided superficial presentations, improper use of examples, and incomplete messages (Tora et al. 2016) ^{28,52} .
Additional non-interventional studies
Parveen S et al. 2016 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) described a participatory communication approach during a Nipah virus outbreak in Bangladesh, using image-based dialogue sessions to explain transmission pathways ⁴¹ . While stigma was not assessed and formal evaluation was limited, the study highlighted the value of culturally tailored, two-way communication in increasing community understanding and trust.
Stakeholder interviews
"So I think it would be better even before the outbreak. Right now, I think that the ministry should make some organisation or some teams, some health workers should be reaching the communities and invite them to know more... Because according to what I see, it seems they have come to be frequent, maybe this year something like cholera may come, another year Ebola may come or any other thing may come." - Interview 28, Ebola disease burial team member and COVID-19 infection control support worker
Affected communities survey
In the Ugandan-cohort open-text responses six respondents suggested that community dialogues should be used rather than 'campaigns' and four respondents suggested that

"good communication between health workers and community" would reduce stigma. Two respondents suggested further involvement of village health teams with one suggesting to "strengthen the VHT teams because they did very good work". One respondent suggested "more education of the community even without outbreaks", with another suggesting that "health education must be continuous".

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	The intervention lacks direct evidence of benefit to affected individuals, population or societal benefit/improving equity in outbreaks. There is indirect evidence of benefit. The main anticipated potential harm is incorrect/incomplete information. Upskilling of community health workers may be helpful for future outbreak response. The intervention may be applicable to a wide range of conditions, potentially increasing net benefit.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	
Uncertain	
Feasibility of integration	The intervention requires careful implementation considerations including funding and human resources. No data were found on cost effectiveness. The intervention may be applicable to a wide range of conditions, potentially increasing cost-effectiveness.
Uncertain	
Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Drawn from stakeholder interviews, indirect reviews of stigma from two chronic infectious diseases of low to moderate quality (AMSTAR 2), one methodologically sound additional non-interventional study, and frequent open text survey response in single context.
Very Low	

Recommended Intervention A5	
We suggest incorporating person-centred features into personal protective equipment design and protocols to minimise depersonalisation.	
Evidence Profile	
Primary evidence from systematic review	
N/A	
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews	
In Driedger M et al. 2018 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) the importance of the patient-physician relationship was consistently emphasised in analysed studies, and suggested that trust, cultural sensitivity, and communication skills can act as facilitators of infectious disease interventions, whereas a negative relationship can serve as a barrier ²³ .	
Additional non-interventional studies	
N/A	
Stakeholder interviews	
<p>"[PPE] is intimately intertwined with stigma in the medical setting because there are patients where you wear the gown, the goggles, the certain type of mask and the hair covering, God knows what. There are certain types of patients who you do that for and certain patients that you don't. And sometimes you might do that because of the stigma associated with that person being infected with that pathogen in question. But sometimes there might be reverse causation, right? That the very fact of putting all this stuff on makes you stigmatise them more. And it's hard for me to believe that doing all this irrational stuff is good for outbreak control. I'm sure it's bad. And I'm sure it's also bad for patients who must feel stigmatised when the doctors won't speak to them with their mask off and their gloves off and their gown off and so on, like they would speak to another human being." - Interview 5, Multi-outbreak health ethicist and policymaker</p> <p>"We've done that in clinical care settings where you have, for example, you have your name written on your forehead so that you're like, I'm a real human who really cares, I'm not just a robot." - Interview 16, Multi-outbreak international response coordinator and public health expert</p>	
Affected communities survey	
In the Ugandan cohort open-text responses one respondent said "Give healthcare workers enough [personal protective equipment] so they can properly touch and care for patients".	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	The intervention lacks evidence of effectiveness from the systematic review and is based on stakeholder interviews, community survey and indirect systematic review results. It is considered unlikely to cause harms. Improved patient-provider
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	

Probably favours intervention	communication may have additional benefits on mental and physical health.
Human rights and acceptability	Acceptability is supported by stakeholder interviews. Intrusiveness was considered low.
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	Stakeholder interviews suggest feasibility but implementation is likely to be affected by design-specific costs. In its simplest form the intervention should be feasible across most outbreak settings.
Neither	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Recommendation is drawn from limited data from stakeholder interviews, single open text community survey response, and moderate quality indirect systematic review (AMSTAR 2).
Overall quality of evidence	
Very low	

Recommended Intervention A6
We suggest collaborating on preparedness activities with community members affected by illnesses or outbreaks with transferable learnings.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
Two studies in Kemp et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) reported on training people living with HIV to conduct community projects ²⁸ . Community members reported finding the project coordination 'challenging' and 'exhausting' but 'interesting'.
Additional non-interventional studies
Musoke D et al. 2025 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) concludes that barriers to community engagement in the Ugandan Ebola disease outbreak included the following: limited consultation due to misbelief in community roles; delayed sociocultural discussions; stigma and delayed psychosocial interventions; misinformation, rumours and political influence; poor communication mechanisms; contradictory messages and lack of transparency; language barrier and inappropriate communication media; work overload for CHWs and other community volunteers; failure to prioritise protection of community workers; lack of compensation for community health workers and other community personnel; poor logistical management; inadequate coordination and partner operations; unfavourable institutional structures; and limited funding for emergencies ³⁹ .
Stakeholder interviews

"I guess again looking for comparisons with similar outbreaks that were associated with stigma and learning lessons from those. So the obvious example for mpox being HIV, the early days of HIV and trying not to repeat the mistakes and looking at what things were done back then. So not reinventing the wheel but looking at things that were done in the past that might be useful this time around." - Interview 3, Multi-outbreak clinical responder and researcher

"We have responded many times. So there was a bit of comfort that we're not going to die, you know." - Ministry of health representative - Interview 22, COVID-19 and Ebola mental health lead and Ministry of Health official

"The trial recruited mainly local people for the social science team and the community engagement team. So that was about building trust and that was sort of quite purposefully done. Also, many of them had already worked on the Ebola response, so they were very, very knowledgeable about stigma and the issues that people suffered and how, you know, people are hidden, or hid away, how they sort of struggled under quarantine with inappropriate care and support services." - Interview 2, Multi-outbreak anthropologist

Affected communities survey

N/A

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	Drawn from stakeholder interviews only therefore limited evidence of effectiveness but positive health equity, population, and societal effects anticipated. Harm is unlikely but there is a potential risk for discrimination related to increased identifiability, overburdening and additional stress for those involved.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	Involving communities supported from a human rights perspective. One indirect systematic review (HIV context) discusses how community members taught to run projects found it challenging and tiring but rewarding.
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	Requires human resourcing and reimbursement/funding to avoid reliance on goodwill and may require training. A related qualitative study highlights several challenges with community engagement in a previous outbreak.
Uncertain	
Feasibility of integration	
Uncertain	
Overall quality of evidence	

Very low	No direct empirical evidence from systematic a review. Recommendation is drawn from stakeholder interviews. One moderate quality indirect systematic reviews (AMSTAR 2) discusses acceptability/feasibility. An additional methodologically sound (CASP) qualitative study discusses challenges.
----------	--

B) Recommended interventions to reduce stigma during outbreak response:

Recommended Intervention B1
We recommend embedding stigma reduction messages in public education and risk communication efforts.
Evidence profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
<p>Moderate certainty evidence (GRADE) from 2 x RCTs^{11,18}. Islam et al. demonstrated that a phone-based information campaign in India significantly reduced COVID-19-related stigma toward patients, religious minorities, lower-caste groups, and frontline workers by correcting misconceptions about disease transmission and prevalence¹¹. In their RCT, Valeri et al. found that participants who received only an informational sheet about COVID-19 did not exhibit significant reductions in stigma compared to no intervention¹⁸. However, those who viewed a video-based intervention addressing COVID-19-related stigma experienced notable decreases in both fear and public stigma compared to the information sheet alone.</p> <p>Low certainty evidence (CERQUAL) from 2 x qualitative studies^{9,10}. Crea et al. found that community education efforts about Ebola disease recovery and reintegration in Sierra Leone, led by trusted local figures like religious leaders and Ebola survivors, helped reduce stigma by addressing misinformation¹⁰. Collier et al. found that in Sierra Leone, community-led efforts, including engagement by local leaders, were more effective in reducing stigma and facilitating reintegration than top-down public health campaigns⁹.</p>
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
<p>Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) recommends that stigma reduction strategies targeting the general public should build on knowledge-shaping and attitude-changing strategies (based on their systematic review) and that mass media should be employed to share balanced and accurate information, focused on avoiding stigma (based on additional material)²⁵. Sengupta S et al. 2011 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) found that interventions involving information dissemination were linked to reduced stigmatising attitudes towards people living with HIV³³. Although outside of the infectious disease context, Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate), report that mass media campaigns to reduce the stigma associated with mental health have been implemented at scale and sustained over time in the England, Scotland, Canada, New Zealand, and Australia; however, most interventions</p>

do not reach those who need them²⁸. They note that this is especially true in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where reduced access to resources and lack of political support for stigma reduction interventions compound the burden and consequences of stigma. In their review Kemp et al. also include a study that provided an educational video on TB stigma and noted that effectiveness was limited by practical issues such as DVD players not having high volume and there were limited electrical outlets; but that video content was understood, and the short duration of video was not disruptive to TB clinic schedules⁵³. Lastly, the Kemp review reports that various film, radio, and mass media anti-stigma interventions were wide-reaching and generally well-received²⁸.

Most reviews that include information provision are unclear about whether education or information provision interventions referred to education about the disease or about associated stigma or both. **Hofstraat K et al. 2016 (AMSTAR 2: Low)**, in their systematic review of social stigma in neglected tropical diseases, concluded that health education interventions are useful to reduce community stigma but noted that to be effective, health education needs to address specific cultural and religious beliefs, and the specific questions and fears that people have in a given community, and needs to be combined with other interventions²⁷. **Sengupta S et al. 2011 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** found that information provision was linked to reduced stigmatising attitudes towards people living with HIV³³. **Stangl AL et al. 2013 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** similarly found that most information related stigma reduction initiatives were effective at reducing stigma³⁴.

Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) recommend that partnering with community leaders is essential to build trust, and develop and implement contextually appropriate anti-stigma strategies due to interpersonal connections promoting reassurance, adding legitimacy to general public health efforts, and disseminating information to those who might mistrust official communication (additional literature) and that an information-based approach, including the involvement of popular opinion leaders, should be implemented to reduce stigma against health workers (systematic review)²⁵. **Nyblade L et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2 Moderate)** describes an intervention that trained facility-based stigma reduction popular opinion leaders to successfully reduce stigma³¹. **Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** report on a study (Rice et al. 2012) which reports that a rise in communication about HIV/STIs in the intervention Chinese markets was substantial when training popular opinion leaders^{28,54}. **Stangl AL et al. 2022 (AMSTAR 2: High)** found that intersectionality-informed, multilevel interventions were generally successful in improving HIV-related health and empowerment outcomes, though stigma reduction effects were more mixed, underscoring the need for more structural approaches⁵⁵.

Additional non-interventional studies

Zalwango MG et al. 2024 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) report that conflicting health messages, such as claims that survivors were both safe and still carried the virus in bodily fluids, contributed to fear and confusion⁴³. They also reported that loudspeaker-based public health education was often inaudible or poorly understood, with respondents suggesting that visual formats (e.g. videos) would be more effective.

In **Person B et al. 2004 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound)** key informants from the 2003 SARS epidemic in the US made a range of recommendations⁴². These included disseminating SARS information through multiple and culturally appropriate channels, including (but not limited to) community visits, town hall meetings, and health education and communication channels to complement mass media messages; and establishing partnerships with local Asian-American community-based organisations to educate the community.

Stakeholder interviews

I think it's important to have consistent messages, like "you need to wear a mask until the pandemic ends" and "we should not stigmatise people who wear masks or who have Covid", consistently and throughout all government agencies, websites and also media. I think it's also important to emotionally show how people with Covid are struggling with their personal life because of stigma..." - Interview 12, COVID-19 social scientist

"When you're doing the community health education, try to also bring in the psychosocial bit of it so that people can be prepared mentally to either get sick or to receive this person." - Interview 13, Medical doctor and Ebola survivor

"We often talk about how the approach to community engagement isn't just a knowledge-deficit approach, which is just if we just tell people enough information that'll be fine. So, you know, very much more working on building this trust than focusing on giving everybody lots of information." - Interview 2, Multi-outbreak anthropologist

"Having a message from us, from a trusted source, where we're more rooted in the community was much more tolerable I guess for the community to listen to than, you know, the government or the National Health Service saying, you know, you guys need to da da da da da thing." -Interview 8, mpox non-governmental response coordinator and community advocate

"Using people that are familiar to [the community], that they know, I think the message is better accepted than bringing people that are foreigners to an area to pass on a message. So local context is very important."- Interview 14, COVID-19 and Ebola disease psychosocial lead and clinical responder

Affected communities survey

More public education and stigma reduction campaigns were consistently the most and second most supported stigma reduction interventions across contexts (90-96% and 76-86% respondents supportive respectively), although the survey did not specify whether this was related to the disease only or also involved stigma awareness. In the free-text options four respondents from Uganda suggested that health talks on the radio and in schools about survivors would be helpful but emphasised that 'talking about survival' needed to be combined with risk communication: "so people are aware when someone is healed ". Other respondents suggested that assurance that survivors are safe would be helpful and that 'the message of "love one another" is vital in the reduction of stigma'. Another respondent in Uganda suggested that faster communication from the government would be helpful while six respondents in Uganda suggested that community dialogues should be used rather than 'campaigns'. Four respondents suggested further involving close relatives, community and religious leaders and key community members, and one respondent

suggested involving local politicians. Another respondent suggested integration into church sermons. Two respondents suggested further involvement of village health team with one suggesting to "strengthen the VHT teams because they did very good work"	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	Moderate certainty evidence shows messaging can reduce stigmatising attitudes. Solidarity and equity impacts are inferred from stakeholder and review data. Effectiveness may depend on clarity and coordination. No harms identified.
Favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Favours intervention	Supported by stakeholder interviews and surveys. Messaging is considered acceptable when empathetic and consistent. Intrusiveness is assessed as low.
Human rights and acceptability	
Favours intervention	Likely low cost and feasible when integrated into existing platforms. National roll out in Kenya of COVID-19 anti-stigma messaging suggests feasibility (Tidwell J 2024).
Financial and economic considerations	
Probably favours intervention	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	Evidence from 2 RCTs (GRADE moderate certainty), 2 systematic reviews of other infectious diseases (1 x AMSTAR high, 1 x AMSTAR low), stakeholder interviews, and community surveys across three contexts.
Overall quality of evidence	
Moderate	

Recommended Intervention B2
We recommend facilitating public engagement with affected individuals' experiences.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
Low certainty evidence (GRADE) from 1 x RCT ¹⁸ ; Very low certainty evidence (CERQual) from 1 x qualitative study ⁹ . In their USA-based RCT, Valeri et al. found brief video interventions (including a 90 second video representing a COVID-19 patient who discusses their experience and concerns about being stigmatised) significantly reduced COVID-19-related fear and stigma ¹⁸ . Collier et al. found that in Sierra Leone, community-led peer education by Ebola survivors was more effective in reducing stigma and facilitating reintegration than top-down public health campaigns ⁹ .
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews

Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) recommend using artists and art to showcase stories, conditions and experiences of people who have suffered discrimination can cultivate engagement, empathy, acceptance and social change (based on additional material)²⁵. **Anindhita M et al. 2024 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** found the use of low-cost, culturally relevant tools such as peer counselling, storytelling, and community videos helped promote awareness and reduce stigma at both individual and community levels²¹. **Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** describe how 'The Stigma Assessment and Reduction of Impact' program in Indonesia reduced stigma by teaching participatory video production skills to people affected by leprosy²⁸. However, the associated study also reports challenges, including related to convincing key stakeholders of the value of contact events, logistical difficulties (weak audio system, inappropriate venue, too many people, and limited time), audience disengagement (tired, less involved), and organisational issues (cancellations, delays)⁵⁶. Another study included in the Kemp review reports that clinic waiting-room HIV storytelling was seen as useful but that patients were often distracted⁵⁷. **Sengupta S et al. 2011 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** found testimonials from people living with HIV were linked to reduced stigmatising attitudes among participants³³. **Nyblade L et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** describes a relevant study which compared educational lectures plus in-person sharing sessions led by people living with HIV against lectures plus interactive games led by research assistants (not living with HIV), finding no significant difference in stigma reduction^{31,58}. Another study in Nyblade et al.'s review compared informational leaflets, short video interventions, and direct-contact seminars involving mental health clients, reporting significantly improved attitudes and behavioural intent only in the video and seminar groups^{31,59}.

Additional non-interventional studies

N/A

Stakeholder interviews

"They took us and we shared our experiences with them. People started thinking and believing that we are now Ebola free." - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead
 "I think that allows for a lot of ownership over [the situation] and you see that a lot with survivorship across a lot of different experiences where people will be like, 'let me tell you my story' and now 'this is my job'. I do find that to be really helpful if people are up for it. I also think that this is a good time to mention just people being, seeing yourself represented, representation in the stakeholders involved in community and making sure people have what they need [is important]. So, for example, Ebola survivors being health educators, ownership over it, right? That's amazing. People who had mpox now being advocates for prevention across the spectrum of disease, having people with Covid who are now researchers." - Interview 4, Multi-outbreak community engagement and public health specialist

"So one of the things that has come out strongly is the use of arts to tackle stigma. So we do a lot of poems, songs, dances as a way of addressing mental health problems. And, one of the ways we do this, for example, how we develop the content, the form, songs and dance, is that we involve people with lived experience, and so they share their oral histories, and then artists come and use that content to develop material. And then this material is what is recorded. And then we do roadshows and door to door visits. Just

talking to people about mental health problems. And we also evaluate this." - Interview 33, Health stigma researcher

"So we invited [community members] to the lab to see why so much blood was taken, what happened to the blood, how it was stored, because they weren't worried about what we did with the blood or the laboratory people, they were concerned the blood would be stolen by witches or traditional healers. So when it came to the Sierra Leone trial, we did a lot of kind of visual work around the amount of blood that's being drawn and lots of discussions about blood drawing and the purpose of it. So yeah, I think it can be mitigated." - Interview 2, Multi-outbreak anthropologist

Affected communities survey

Across contexts, the majority of respondents believed that opportunities to hear the stories of people who have recovered would help reduce stigma (83% in Uganda, 73% in Bangladesh and 51% in the UK). In the Ugandan survey open-text responses two respondents suggested further involvement of survivors, with one respondent saying "survivors will be more trusted than health workers". Another respondent said "get people to meet Ebola survivors then they will see they are the same". In the UK one respondent wrote "actually someone physically saying 'it happened to me'".

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	There is low certainty direct evidence that public engagement with the experiences of affected individuals can reduce stigma. Indirect systematic reviews support benefits for empathy, social inclusion, and awareness. Equity gains are inferred through humanisation of affected groups. However, there may be risks of unintended identification or further discrimination if not carefully managed.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	
Neither	
Feasibility of integration	Likely low cost and feasible with appropriate planning and technical support. Reimbursement or compensation for involved community members should be accounted for. Feasibility may vary by setting, format, and access to technology.
Probably yes	
Overall quality of evidence	Evidence is from 1 RCT (GRADE Low), 1 qualitative study (CERQUAL Very Low), moderate-high quality systematic reviews from other infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2),
Moderate	

	stakeholder interviews, and community survey responses across three contexts. Coherence across sources informed a final moderate confidence rating.
--	---

Recommended Intervention B3

We recommend offering accessible psychosocial support and resources to those affected by the outbreak, such as remote services during isolation.

Evidence Profile

Primary evidence from systematic review

Moderate certainty evidence (GRADE) from 2 x RCT^{13,16}. Techapoonpon et al. demonstrated that a brief online destigmatisation program in Thailand significantly reduced COVID-19-related stigma among survivors within two weeks post-discharge from hospital¹⁶. Lu et al. demonstrated that a brief reading-and-writing-based intervention significantly reduced perceived discrimination among Chinese college students returning home from Wuhan during COVID-19, by enhancing their perceived social support¹³.

Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews

Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) emphasise that the link between stigma and COVID-19, and its impact, should be considered for people who have a current confirmed COVID-19 diagnosis, and also people who have been in COVID-19 quarantine, received COVID-19 treatment, and people associated with COVID-19 due to their work, ethnicity or country of origin, or an affiliation with a person who is unwell or otherwise associated with the virus²⁵. Interventions to support and provide encouragement/counselling for those on COVID-19 frontlines are strongly recommended (based on chronic infectious disease systematic review). **Anindhita M et al. 2024 (AMSTAR 2 Moderate)** found that community-based psychosocial support interventions—particularly those delivered by trained laypersons or peers—were found to reduce internalised, enacted, anticipated, and self-stigma among individuals affected by HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and leprosy²¹. They emphasised the need for adequate training for lay and recovered persons.

Nyblade L et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) reports on Clarke S et al. 2015 who compared “dialectical behavioural therapy,” which aims to reduce prejudice and discrimination towards patients with personality disorders by providing staff with knowledge and skills to improve the effectiveness of their clinical practice, to “acceptance and commitment training,” which aims to provide self-management skills to reduce the impact of negative evaluations and strengthen value-driven behaviour^{31,60}. For both types of training, staff attitudes improved and social distancing reduced, but they did not significantly differ. **Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** report that after a leprosy counselling intervention, participants appreciated counselling; but counsellors needed intense supervision, it was not easy to manage client conditions and characteristics; peer counsellors were preferred and family counselling preferred overall, but integrating family, individual, and group counselling was best approach²⁸. The distance between clients was seen as a barrier for lay

counsellors⁶¹. Also in the Kemp review, a study of HIV support groups in Tanzania reported patients judged usefulness 4.76 out of 5⁶².

Stangl AL et al. 2013 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) also found that group-based and peer-led psychosocial interventions in HIV contexts were effective in reducing internalised stigma, and emphasised the importance of tailoring and sustained delivery³⁴.

Additional non-interventional studies

N/A

Stakeholder interviews

"The psychosocial base right from the beginning of testing someone... that is one thing we should do to reduce the stigma. The people need to be talked to, and before they are tested."
- Interview 26, COVID-19 and Ebola disease clinical responder and mental health lead

"The psychosocial team used to come three times in a day. They come in the morning, they pray for you. They assure you... and you become friends. They tell you to stop thinking this and that. They tell you how others have come out of the ETU. That experience made me strong and it was really enough support." - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead

Affected communities survey

75%, 63% and 41% of respondents supported the suggestion of psychological support as a stigma reduction measure in Uganda (Ebola), Bangladesh (Nipah) and UK (mpox) respectively.

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	There is moderate certainty direct evidence that digitally administered psychosocial support can reduce perceived stigma in the short term. Indirect reviews support potential equity and population health benefits, particularly for affected individuals, caregivers, and frontline workers. No harms identified. Sustained benefit beyond 28 days has not been demonstrated in outbreak contexts.
Favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	Stakeholder interviews and survey data suggest high acceptability when interventions are timely, confidential, and tailored to affected groups. However, in some contexts, accessing formal mental health or social services may itself be associated with stigma. Intrusiveness is low.
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	Implementation may require investment in trained personnel, supervision, and coordination, even if digital materials are low
Probably favours business as usual	
Feasibility of integration	

Probably favours intervention	cost. Feasibility depends on available human resources and digital access.
Overall quality of evidence	Evidence from 2 RCTs (GRADE Moderate), supported by 4 moderate-high systematic reviews from other infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2), stakeholder interviews, survey question across three contexts.
Moderate	

Recommended Approach B4

We recommend co-designing, adapting and implementing stigma awareness initiatives for the local context with affected community members, including people with lived experience of the illness.

Evidence Profile

Primary evidence from systematic review

Moderate certainty evidence (CERQUAL) from 2 x qualitative studies^{8,9}. Biesty et al. found that during the 2022–2023 UK mpox outbreak, community-led health promotion efforts by LGBTQ+ organisations and local sexual health clinics effectively mitigated stigma and encouraged health-seeking behaviours among men who have sex with men⁸. Collier et al. found that in Sierra Leone, community-led efforts, particularly peer education by Ebola survivors and engagement by local leaders, were more effective in reducing stigma and facilitating reintegration than top-down public health campaigns⁹.

Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews

Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) recommend that affected community members should be actively involved in shaping media language, based on additional material in their review of chronic infectious diseases, and that interventions should build on positive, community-proposed coping strategies (also based on additional material)²⁵. They emphasise tailoring communication strategies to address specific local misconceptions, myths, and stereotypes (based on their review findings), and ensuring targeted interventions for disadvantaged or marginalised groups who are particularly vulnerable to stigma and exclusion (based on additional material).

Anindhita M et al. 2024 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) similarly found that stigma reduction interventions that actively engaged affected communities from design through to implementation were more acceptable, effective, and sustainable across contexts including HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and leprosy²¹.

Hofstraat K et al. 2016 (AMSTAR 2: Low) concluded that educational interventions for neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) were more effective when explicitly addressing specific local cultural and religious beliefs²⁷.

Additional non-interventional studies

In **Person B et al. 2004 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound)** key informants from the 2003 SARS epidemic in the US made a range of recommendations including 1) developing

simple, tailored SARS prevention messages; and 2) developing SARS information materials in various Asian languages⁴². In an agenda-setting, multi-disciplinary roundtable convened to examine experiences and implications of the West Africa Ebola disease epidemic for health systems in Ghana, healthcare workers recommended prioritising engaging directly with key community groups to co-produce contextually relevant educational messages to help 'decrease stigma, fear, and the demoralizing perception that the disease defies remedy or control' (**Nyarko Y et al. 2015 [CASP: Mostly methodologically sound]**)⁴⁰.

Musoke D et al. 2025 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) concludes that barriers to community engagement in the Ugandan Ebola disease outbreak included: limited consultation due to misbelief in community roles; delayed sociocultural discussions; stigma and delayed psychosocial interventions; misinformation, rumours and political influence; poor communication mechanisms; contradictory messages and lack of transparency; language barrier and inappropriate communication media; work overload for community health workers and other community volunteers; failure to prioritise protection of community workers; lack of compensation for community health workers and other community personnel; poor logistical management; inadequate coordination and partner operations; unfavourable institutional structures; and limited funding for emergencies³⁹.

Stakeholder interviews

"When this happened, cholera happened in the Middle East. Well, there it was completely different message that the messages that we used to bring in when it comes to DRC, for example. So there you have to adapt. You have to try to understand who does the community trust or doesn't trust. Mobilize, building up something. First, you didn't expect that outbreak and two, very quickly, you need to start building up that communication lines and try to understand who is the one influencing the community so as to make sure the messages get there at the right time and with the right message." - Interview 24, Multi-outbreak international response senior leadership

"I think crafting messaging that is appropriate, easily understandable in the locally spoken languages goes a long way in minimising stigma. And also having engagement of ongoing nature because it's not enough for you to do a community drive in a community and consider that you have covered that community and the stigma levels have been reduced." - Interview 14, COVID-19 and Ebola disease psychosocial lead and clinical responder

Affected communities survey

"More thoughtful public health messages" was supported by 81%, 69%, and 73% of respondents in Uganda, UK, and Bangladesh respectively. In Bangladesh two respondents suggested in the free text that they believed 'door-to-door' dissemination would be more effective. In the Ugandan open responses respondents had a range of suggestions for making interventions more locally appropriate: six respondents suggested that community dialogues should be used rather than 'campaigns'. Another respondent said "Whenever community hear announcements on radio they say ah they've started their same things. If you print so many billboards the community attitude will not change. The reading culture is poor. We need meetings where community members can ask silly questions." One respondent had suggestions regarding distribution of risk communication teams, suggesting 'more sensitisation for those far away from the cases' as 'those close have got

enough' and two respondents suggested community meetings. In the UK open-text responses, one respondent suggested "As with HIV stigma, awareness of those in groups not deemed "high risk" or those that feel low-risk.

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	Moderate confidence from qualitative studies, indirect reviews, and stakeholder interviews suggests co-design can improve trust, reduce stigma, and support inclusion. Benefits for equity and societal cohesion are inferred.
Favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	Stakeholder interviews, community surveys, and review data support high acceptability when participation is voluntary, inclusive, and respectful. Intrusiveness is low, though risks related to visibility and identifiability must be managed.
Favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	Likely feasible and low cost if planned in advance and appropriately resourced. Barriers include time constraints, poor coordination, and over-reliance on unpaid or overstretched community actors. It is likely to result in messages reaching communities more effectively therefore saving costs of more extensive, ineffective communication methods.
Probably favours intervention	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	
Overall quality of evidence	Evidence from 2 qualitative studies (CERQUAL moderate), multiple systematic reviews from other infectious diseases, three additional non-interventional studies, stakeholder interviews and community surveys across three contexts.
Moderate	

Recommended Intervention B5

We suggest facilitating peer support opportunities led by people with lived experience.

Evidence Profile

Primary evidence from systematic review

N/A

Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews

In **Anindhita M et al. 2024 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** most studies involved lay people in the community as supporters of those affected²¹. The predominant reported mechanism of intervention effect was the ability of supporters to enable those affected to feel seen and listened to, to accept their diagnosis, to improve their self-esteem, and to facilitate continuation of their daily lives, and thereby reducing anticipated stigma, self-stigma, and mental illness. Adequate training was reported to be essential to ensure success of interventions. An HIV study in **Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** found that participants reported testimonials and role-modeling to be encouraging and gave them courage to disclose, though some concerns about group testing and disclosure process were expressed^{28,63}. Another study in the Kemp review found that leaders of an HIV peer support group continued activities post-funding⁶⁴.

Additional non-interventional studies

N/A

Stakeholder interviews

"There are communities of women who moved to start their own communities for raising their kids with congenital Zika syndrome because they needed to feel a sense of comfort in a community." - Interview 4, Multi-outbreak community engagement and public health specialist

"We [Ebola survivors] did also play a role in ending stigma and discrimination because I created an association of survivors and now we started moving around churches, mosques, public places... It is still moving and is still on the ground fighting discrimination and stigma." - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead

"All our goals in peer support are heavily based on this: many communities only go to the doctor very secretly. Don't talk to anyone, only talk to the doctor and then leave the clinic to never be seen again. You cannot find those people to talk about sex or go and pick up a test or just, you know, pick up a condom somewhere. They would never do such a thing. That's why we say that, you know, they're there, where those people go frequently, GPs or sexual health clinics, so we should be there as peer support, as people living with that condition. So kind of catch with those people in the clinic when they are there. So saying that, you know, this is not something that you should be afraid of to beat that anticipated stigma." - Interview 7, Community advocate with lived experience of HIV and mpox

Affected communities survey

N/A

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm

Probably favours intervention

Health equity/non-discrimination

Probably favours intervention

Societal implications

No direct evidence of effectiveness. Stakeholder interviews and indirect evidence from established infectious diseases suggest peer support may reduce stigma-related distress, support recovery, and promote social connection. Potential harms

Probably favours intervention	include overidentification, re-traumatisation, or stigmatisation of peer supporters.
Human rights and acceptability	Supported by stakeholder interviews. Acceptability likely depends on local norms and delivery. Participation must be voluntary. Intrusiveness may vary depending on context and level of visibility.
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	Training, supervision, and ongoing support are needed to ensure feasibility and prevent overburdening peer mentors but likely more cost-effective than professional services. Indirect evidence from HIV suggests peer-led approaches can be sustained over time if well integrated.
Probably favours intervention	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	
Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews and one indirect systematic review of other infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2 Moderate).
Very low	

Recommended Intervention B6

We suggest against introducing community protection bylaws that impose fines for stigmatisation of affected persons.

Evidence Profile

Primary evidence from systematic review

Very low certainty evidence (CERQUAL) from 1 x qualitative study¹⁰. Crea et al. found that community protection bylaws in Sierra Leone, created with local leaders, helped reduce Ebola-related stigma by discouraging discrimination and supporting survivor reintegration¹⁰.

Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews

Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) recommended that, based on additional literature, excessive policing or criminalising the breaching of COVID-19-related health policies is likely to increase stigma and discrimination, and risks loss of trust which may in turn reduce compliance with such measures or lead to protests (based on additional literature)²⁵. In **Stangl AL et al. 2013 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** discussion, they mention that legal education and legal aid services are often needed to support PLHIV to access justice, and such services are recommended by UNAIDS as critical and suggest that evaluation data are needed to inform the wider use of such approaches to support the positive advances that have been made in the public policy arena in many countries³⁴. In **Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate)** one study reports HIV crisis management teams supported 92% of rights violations in redress^{28,65}.

Additional non-interventional studies	
N/A	
Stakeholder interviews	
<p>"During that time, the [village health team members (VHTs)], I and the rest of the team, we did our work. We are the first people to go on the ground and sensitize before the doctors came in because we were meeting at the health center there, but before they are coming, we just had to go and first sensitize these people. By the time the doctors came when they were aware. Because there was a situation, there is a man here who got a panga. He said "You, you're not entitled to come into my home. I don't want you to go in." So we were the VHTs, before the coming of the doctors, we went to talk to him, smoothly yeah, not rude." - Interview 36, Ebola disease and COVID-19 community health (village health team) worker</p> <p>"Law enforcement can actually be incredibly supportive and useful, but, um, and they can take on more tasks than they probably should, but they need to be informed. Um. And you certainly don't want them reinforcing stigma." - Interview 11, Multi-outbreak response coordinator and researcher</p>	
Affected communities survey	
More laws to stop discrimination was the least supported stigma reduction intervention across the three contexts (49% in Uganda (Ebola), 36% in UK (mpox), and 27% in Bangladesh (Nipah).	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	The intervention's effectiveness is unclear, with mixed evaluations from limited evidence. Overly punitive measures may result in risks of increased discrimination and erosion of trust.
Uncertain	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Uncertain	
Societal implications	Public support in surveys for 'more laws to stop discrimination' is low across three contexts. Stakeholder interviews suggest preference for community-led approaches over law enforcement. Fines may face resistance due to concerns about cultural sensitivity and human rights.
Uncertain	
Human rights and acceptability	Implementing and following up on fines is potentially costly. Community engagement may offer a more feasible and cost-effective alternative.
Probably favours business as usual	
Financial and economic considerations	
Probably favours business as usual	Feasibility of integration
Feasibility of integration	
Uncertain	

Overall quality of evidence	Evidence from 1 qualitative study (CERQUAL Very low) and mixed evidence from stakeholder interviews and systematic reviews from other infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2 High x 1, Moderate x 2) and opposing evidence from survey responses across three contexts.
Very low	

Recommended Intervention B7	
We support further research on the stigma impact, feasibility, and acceptability of community-based quarantine, isolation, and care.	
Evidence Profile	
Primary evidence from systematic review	
N/A	
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews	
N/A	
Additional non-interventional studies	
<p>A COVID-19 modelling study predicted 57% reduction with institutional isolation in comparison to 20% reduction through home-based isolation⁶⁶. A modelling study from Hong-Kong shows similar efficacy in later phases⁶⁷. A study from Qatar found significantly higher rates of depression and anxiety symptoms for respondents in institutional quarantine⁶⁸; lack of contact with family was considered the most important reason for distress. A study exploring experience of institutional quarantine for COVID-19 in Uganda found stigma on return to communities was a major concern⁶⁹. A qualitative evidence synthesis found that strategies to increase adherence to quarantine should be effectively communicated by public health and other agencies involved (e.g., identification of symptoms, risk of transmission, specific actions to take in different scenarios), community oriented (e.g., working with local partnerships with groups to understand needs), provide financial compensation, food provision, social and psychological support, and mitigate against harms (e.g., stigma, social isolation, and vulnerable groups)⁷⁰. A systematic review of mass quarantine found stigma attached for institutional and self isolation across Ebola disease and SARS⁷¹. A study of close contacts quarantined in China further explores the stigma implications of quarantine⁷².</p>	
Stakeholder interviews	
<p><i>In support:</i></p> <p>"I believe that for Ebola outbreaks there's been a lot of learning that has been made, and approaches trying to facilitate home based care by relatives. You know, that's something that for sure has changed the impact... the factor of giving the agency to the family, the affected by the disease family, to care for their people and be active in such a way that they could respond, you know, to their social mandate by their community and improve the</p>	

chances for survival. Yeah. I believe that has been a very good track, and I hope it doesn't stop." - Interview 23, Multi-outbreak international response senior leadership

"Initially people believed they were being rounded up for other reasons. And you know, nothing to do with their health. You see, we adopted a strategy where if a person was a contact, a high risk contact we thought it better to have them in the set up quarantine sites so that we monitor them. And the earliest they get symptoms we can rush them or test them and quickly take them to a treatment unit. Because, you know, the earlier you present to the treatment unit, the higher your chances of survival... But initially they were really so negative about being put in the quarantine. And we had several [people] jump out. They jumped the fence and ran away. Yes, maybe about 2 or 3 if I remember well." - Interview 15, Viral haemorrhagic fever clinical responder and trainer

In opposition:

"What are the conditions necessary to be able to impose a lockdown because there are certain conditions that were not present for a lockdown to be able to work. What did they do? Because they, I mean, people who don't have money. Subsistence workers, they can't buy food to store. They don't have fridges. And even in the tropics. I mean, how is the idea of a house in Europe different to the idea of a house in the tropics? I mean, in the tropics, you live outside. You only go into your house to sleep or to store your goods. So when you introduce lockdowns like that, people would necessarily not be able to comply. So they sent the police and the army. Which is further fear..." "So with mental health, what happened was, you know, at some point there were all these mental health hospitals, which were the isolation type of type of care. Started from the colonial times... And so the modern approach is we now use community based mental health. The only thing is that the communities haven't been, you know, helped to reintegrate. So you empty the mental health hospitals and you throw these people on the community. But there hasn't been sufficient preparation, awareness and even sometimes just physical [preparation]... Yeah, that's community based mental health. But is that community ready? So, yes, engagement, but engagement that is accompanied by safe spaces. Those are the kind of things that I would think of." - Interview 21, Multi-outbreak health ethicist

Affected communities survey

N/A

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm

Favours neither

Health equity/non-discrimination

Favours neither

Societal implications

Favours neither

The intervention's effectiveness is unclear, with mixed evaluations from stakeholder interviews. Benefits include potential improvements in dignity and agency and reduced alienation from their social systems. However, risks include the potential for increased burden on households, particularly in low-resource or overcrowded settings and delayed medical care. Without adequate

	preparation, physical conditions, and social support, home-based quarantine may also pose safety risks. The appropriateness of this intervention varies by pathogen and setting, and its impact on stigma reduction is not well explored.
Human rights and acceptability	Stakeholder interviews suggest mixed acceptability. Some respondents support home-based quarantine, viewing it as a more dignified and acceptable approach compared to institutional quarantine, which has been associated with fear and mistrust. However, concerns were raised about the capacity of households to manage quarantine effectively, particularly in settings where resources are limited or where communities are not prepared. The acceptability of this approach is heavily dependent on local conditions, including the availability of social support and appropriate infrastructure.
Uncertain	
Financial and economic considerations	The financial feasibility of implementing home-based quarantine is uncertain. While it may reduce the need for institutional facilities, it requires significant preparation and support to ensure safety and efficacy. The financial burden on healthcare facilities may be relieved, but the impact on households, especially in low-resource settings, is an important consideration.
Favours neither	
Feasibility of integration	
Uncertain	
Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews only.
Very low	

C) Recommended interventions to reduce stigma during outbreak recovery:

Recommended Intervention C1
We suggest implementing initiatives that help people who have recovered reintegrate into their households, workplaces, schools, religious practices, and other community activities.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
One review within Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) found that workplace anti-stigma interventions in 11 studies consistently had a significant positive impact on employees' supportive behaviour (except one study with only a marginally significant effect) ²⁵ . Driedger M et al. 2018 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) found that time spent accessing healthcare can incur a significant opportunity cost on migrants, especially when they are in a precarious employment situation ²³ .
Additional non-interventional studies
N/A
Stakeholder interviews
"And then we've also been involved in various ways in kind of community re-entry or destigmatisation of survivors. So kind of helping those people to re-enter their communities and kind of be re-accepted into their communities, recognising that stigma was an enormous thing that they suffered, having already, you know, survived a very challenging time." - Interview 16, Multi-outbreak international response coordinator and public health expert "So I remember there was a leaflet from friends and family of returned workers and there was a web page as well to try and explain to them what, what the risk is and mixing with someone who's returned from doing Ebola response work. I certainly used that and I think it did help in some cases. I think some of the media coverage as well, you know, around some of the international workers who got infected and then people supporting them through social media and things and explaining that actually the risks to anybody is incredibly low and that, you know, they're in returning worker schemes and things like that." - Interview 3, Multi-outbreak clinical responder and researcher "Everyone was scared. Not until the psychosocial team came in and told them that place is now Ebola free. You can cut his hair. He will not affect you. He's free from Ebola. And now I think that on the fifth day the psychosocial team came in to support me and now my hair was cut short." - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead
Affected communities survey
In the UK open-text responses, one respondent wrote "As with HIV stigma, awareness of those in groups not deemed 'high risk'". Another respondent wrote "Now that we are

familiar with covid, I think we accept diseases and recovery a bit more as a society, maybe likening it to that experience of not being contagious after X amount of time".	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	No direct evidence, but stakeholder interviews and indirect evidence from established infectious disease reviews suggest this approach may help reduce community-level stigma, prevent exclusion from work, school, and religious life, and improve equity. No harm likely if communication is well-managed. Commonly reported informally in organisational reports but no robust evaluations.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	
Probably favours intervention	
Feasibility of integration	Likely moderate cost. May require coordination across sectors and development of clear public-facing materials. However, more adverse economic consequences anticipated from affected persons missing or losing employment or education.
Probably favours intervention	
Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews, 2 systematic reviews of other infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2 High-Moderate), open text survey responses from one context.
Very low	

Recommended Intervention C2
We suggest including assessment of psychosocial wellbeing as part of follow-up care for people who have recovered and offering referral to longer-term support services.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews

N/A (usually no recovery phase but evidence for psychosocial support during illness may indirectly apply)	
Additional non-interventional studies	
N/A	
Stakeholder interviews	
<p>"I think sometimes when you have a patient in front of you who clearly is describing, you know, really pretty appalling behaviour towards them because they've got TB or HIV or any other infectious disease. I think often being able to say that's quite severe, you know, there is support and then using that to maybe triage the support you can provide them. I think HIV has been very good as a community because most HIV services I've worked with do have some level of support, whether it's peer support or connecting you to psychologists or trying to provide something and making sure that the clinicians who provide that care are trained in it as well is really useful." - Interview 10, Multi-outbreak clinical responder and researcher</p> <p>"These people suffered quite a lot, even those who survived got the stigma that came from the community. There are those who are even contemplating suicide one, because they have lost livelihood, financial losses and now stigma. And of course they felt like I've been taken back to a community that failed to embrace them... The psychosocial support team does the neighbours and more settlement psychosocial arrangements. However, that's not enough. A one day or two day thing is not enough. It's something that needs to be ongoing." - Interview 27, Ebola disease and COVID-19 clinical responder and Ebola survivor programme lead</p>	
Affected communities survey	
75%, 63%, and 41% of respondents supported the suggestion of psychological support as a stigma reduction measure in Uganda (Ebola), Bangladesh (Nipah) and UK (mpox) respectively.	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	No direct evidence of effectiveness. Stakeholder interviews suggest this may help reduce stigma-related distress and support recovery, with potential benefits for equity. No harms identified.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	Prioritised in stakeholder interviews across two contexts. Supported in community survey responses varies across settings. Intrusiveness is likely low to intermediate depending on delivery.
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	

Favours neither	Requires trained personnel and coordination across sectors, but necessary referral points likely already in place. Feasibility may depend on existing service infrastructure and funding availability.
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	
Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews and mixed support from community surveys only.
Very low	

Recommended Intervention C3
We suggest documenting, robustly evaluating, and publishing stigma reduction efforts.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
All reviews note that higher quality studies are needed. Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) suggests that 'research efforts should attempt to avoid the common limitations of stigma research, such as small-scale studies, heterogeneous designs, mixed methodological quality, lack of contextually and culturally adapted interventions, unvalidated outcome measures, limited evaluation of long-term impacts of interventions and behavioural outcomes, and limited evidence from low- and middle-income settings ²⁵ . Methodologically sound research generates stronger evidence, and increased harmonisation across studies would allow for the results to be pooled using robust synthesis methods for increased impact.' Sengupta S et al. 2011 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) note the generally low quality of the studies reviewed ³³ . Kemp CG et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) found that the quality of reporting of implementation outcomes in stigma interventions was low ²⁸ . Stangl AL et al. 2013 (AMSTAR 2: Moderate) conclude that critical challenges and gaps remain which are impeding the identification of effective stigma-reduction strategies that can be implemented by national governments on a larger scale and that the development, validation, and consistent use of globally relevant scales of stigma and discrimination are a critical next step for advancing the field of research in this area ³⁴ . They also state that studies comparing the effectiveness of different stigma-reduction strategies and studies assessing the influence of stigma reduction on key behavioural and biomedical outcomes are also needed to maximise biomedical prevention efforts. Rao D et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2: Low) report that fewer than half of included stigma reduction studies reported measures of practical significance (i.e., effect size) ³² .
Additional non-interventional studies
Ford CL et al. (2021) emphasise the need for active monitoring ³⁷ . They report that systems that monitor racism report historical data on, for instance, hate crimes, but do not capture current patterns, and it is unclear how representative the findings are. Though existing

surveillance systems offer important strengths for monitoring health conditions or racism and related stigma, new surveillance strategies are needed to monitor their intersecting relationships more rigorously.

Stakeholder interviews

"I think evaluation is also something that a lot of outbreaks don't do. Lessons learned, what could go better, and having some type of sustainability of, okay, we know that these things pop up. Let's make sure that we have required training. We have these populations still exist where the continued efforts. And so yes, I would say social science evaluation and sustainability, when done correctly, can really create a system that is able to handle any epidemic or outbreak. But when it's handled on a case by case basis, it's not going to work."
- Interview 4, Multi-outbreak social and behavioural scientist

"We need to find the best tool to use to assess whether issues of stigma are being addressed during the outbreak or after the outbreak." - Interview 26, COVID-19 and Ebola disease clinical responder and mental health lead

Affected communities survey

N/A

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	No direct evidence of effectiveness. Stakeholder interviews and multiple systematic reviews from established infectious diseases highlight the lack of high-quality evaluation as a barrier to identifying effective stigma reduction strategies. Documenting and evaluating interventions may improve learning, inform future responses, and promote more effective and equitable implementation. No harms identified.
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Probably favours intervention	
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	
Financial and economic considerations	
Probably favours intervention	
Feasibility of integration	Feasibility may depend on the availability of funding, research capacity, and integration into existing monitoring systems. Mixed methods and implementation research approaches can be resource-intensive but offer insights into both outcomes and
Probably favours intervention	

	context. The intervention will save on small, unknowingly duplicated, ineffective efforts.
Overall quality of evidence	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews and all available indirect systematic reviews of established infectious diseases. Prioritisation supported by one 'rapid environmental scan'.
Very low	

Recommended Intervention C4	
We support further research on the effectiveness, acceptability, and potential harms of facilitating visible contact between response workers and recovered persons.	
Evidence Profile	
Primary evidence from systematic review	
N/A	
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews	
N/A	
Additional non-interventional studies	
N/A	
Stakeholder interviews	
<p>"So [the health workers] even came at my home place, they called the neighbours. They had a talk with them. They had to educate them for about 30 minutes. Um, they called me out of the house. They were with me. They even did the handshake when the other village mates were seeing. We even sat together on a bench with them. So this is when people, I think, started picking up that if these health workers can sit with him, they can have a handshake with him, then that's meaning he could be Ebola free." - Interview 30, Ebola survivor and peer support lead</p> <p>"You know, a small gesture, like a handshake, to a survivor, is a big deal to them" - Interview 27, Ebola and COVID-19 clinical responder and Ebola survivor programme lead</p>	
Affected communities survey	
In the open-text responses, one Ugandan-based respondent suggested that more assurance that survivors are safe was needed, saying 'health workers will be more trusted than survivors.'	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	No direct evidence from outbreak-related systematic review. Stakeholder interviews (mostly referring to the context of Ebola
Probably favours intervention	
Health equity/non-discrimination	

Probably favours intervention	disease) suggest that symbolic gestures may reduce fear, demonstrate safety, and support reintegration. Potential benefits include reducing stigma-related distress and promoting community reassurance. Possible harms include privacy concerns and unwanted attention.
Societal implications	
Probably favours intervention	Acceptability appears high in stakeholder accounts, provided actions are voluntary and coordinated with the affected person (but again only in relation to Ebola disease). Intrusiveness may vary depending on local norms and the visibility of the gesture. Aligns with principles of dignity and social inclusion.
Human rights and acceptability	
Probably favours intervention	Low cost and likely feasible in most settings. Requires coordination and prior consent but can be integrated into existing risk communication or psychosocial support activities.
Financial and economic considerations	
Favours neither	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews and single open text survey response only.
Overall quality of evidence	
Very low	

Intervention C5
We support further research on the effectiveness, acceptability, and potential harms of recovery celebrations.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
N/A
Additional non-interventional studies
N/A
Stakeholder interviews
"One thing I saw that was really good was the survivor wall at one of the camps, where every survivor when they came out so when they leave the red zone. They have a shower and they're given new clothes and they have a party . They have an African band and they celebrate the survival. And then they had a survivors' wall where every survivor put their hand

in paint and put a handprint on the wall. And then you had this big survivors' wall and all the colors. And so it was a real effort to not talk about the deaths, but talk about the survivors and celebrate the survivors. And you could see the survivors. I've got photographs of all the hand handprints, you know, like the opposite of the Covid wall in London. So we have a survivor wall, all the people who survived it, you know, and talk about the positives. And then, you know, there's lots of instances of posters. And I remember in Sierra Leone, there was a really catchy song that you could always hear in the buses about Ebola." - Interview 9, Multi-outbreak clinical research lead

"We had some situations where the family was educated and prepared very well, and we actually found that they had even prepared a party, a small party for the survivor coming back home. And then the other families, of course, where you did not prepare them, like people just even run away from the neighborhood because of someone coming back from the treatment unit. So that part of it is very, very, very important." - Interview 13, Medical doctor and Ebola survivor

"In West Africa, this was, it was under the kind of umbrella of psychosocial support. And was looking at first off, trying to make it a celebratory event. So having a kind of homecoming event when survivors come back into their communities singing and dancing and what have you, just to make it a joyous thing. And that would be coupled with information and education around, you know, who is and is not a risk of spreading Ebola. What are the symptoms? How does it spread?" - Interview 16, Multi-outbreak international response coordinator and public health expert

Affected communities survey

One Uganda-based respondent suggested that they "should have a day gazetted for National Ebola celebration".

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	Very low-quality evidence from stakeholder interviews suggests that recovery celebrations can help with social reintegration and reduce stigma. However, risks include unwanted visibility or pressure to participate, particularly for individuals who might not feel ready for public recognition or who prefer a lower-profile reintegration process. There is also a risk of being insensitive to those who have lost a loved one.
Uncertain	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Uncertain	
Societal implications	Generally supported by stakeholders, requires emphasis on voluntary participation and respect for individual preferences regarding public visibility. Intrusiveness assessed as intermediate.
Uncertain	
Human rights and acceptability	Generally supported by stakeholders, requires emphasis on voluntary participation and respect for individual preferences regarding public visibility. Intrusiveness assessed as intermediate.
Probably favours intervention	

Financial and economic considerations	Some costs are likely to be attached but may be low-cost and feasible with proper planning and coordination. May allow faster re-entry into the workplace.
Uncertain	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews and a single open-text survey response only.
Overall quality of evidence	
Very low	

X) Interventions discussed but no recommendation made:

Intervention X1	
Implementing recovery certificates.	
Evidence Profile	
Primary evidence from systematic review	
N/A	
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews	
N/A	
Additional non-interventional studies	
<p>Fargnoli V et al. 2021 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) assessed acceptability of COVID-19 recovery certificates in Geneva, Switzerland, and found that few participants considered immunity certificates based on serological testing as an acceptable public health measure³⁶. Major concerns included the reliability of scientific data related to COVID-19 immunity and serological testing, potential re-infection, as well as the possibility that the use of certificates could result in deleterious outcomes. Discrimination, counterfeiting, incitement for self-infection, invasion of the private sphere, violation of personal integrity, and violation of medical privacy were perceived as the major risks. Immunity certificates were considered more acceptable when in relation to vaccination, particularly for protection in certain contexts involving leisure or work-related activities.</p>	
Stakeholder interviews	
<p>"I think there was a perception that [recovery certificates] were helpful and they wanted to have something that they could take back and say, Look, it's got the hospital stamp on it, it's official, I'm no longer infectious." - Interview 11, Multi-outbreak response coordinator and researcher</p>	
Affected communities survey	
<p>There was a wide range in support for recovery certificates as a stigma reduction measure (72% in Uganda, 47% in Bangladesh, 19% in UK). One respondent in Uganda said 'even wives want recovery certificates'.</p>	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	<p>The intervention's effectiveness is unclear, with mixed evaluations from limited evidence. Recovery certificates have been perceived as helpful in some settings, providing official reassurance of non-infectiousness. However, they may increase the risk of unwanted disclosure or reinforce identifiability.</p> <p>Acceptability and value varies widely by survey. Intermediate intrusiveness.</p>
Uncertain	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Uncertain	
Societal implications	
Favours neither	
Human rights and acceptability	<p>Acceptability and value varies widely by survey. Intermediate intrusiveness.</p>
Uncertain	

Financial and economic considerations	Recovery certificates are likely to be low-cost and feasible, but implementation may require coordination across sectors.
Favours neither	
Feasibility of integration	
Probably favours intervention	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews, mixed findings from survey responses across contexts. One methodologically sound qualitative study assessing acceptability. Limited coherence.
Overall quality of evidence	
Very low	

Intervention X2
Implementing population-wide outbreak control measures to avoid targeted restrictions.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
Very low certainty evidence (GRADE) from 1 x observational study ¹² . Kwon et al. found that early in the COVID-19 pandemic, mask wearers in the USA experienced more perceived discrimination than non-wearers, but after August 2020, and the introduction of state-level mask mandates, this trend reversed ¹² . Discriminatory experiences were higher where participants acted in opposition to state mandates (e.g., wore a mask with no mandate, did not wear a mask with mandates in place).
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
Gronholm PC et al. 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High) recommended that universal public health strategies (e.g. testing; stimulus checks; policies like physical distancing, travel bans and quarantine) can reduce stigma (vs. targeted strategies, which can imply blame on particular individuals/groups) ²⁵ . Nyblade L et al. 2019 (AMSTAR 2 Moderate) describes an intervention that trained facility-based stigma reduction popular opinion leaders on universal precaution procedures and provided infection protection supplies, such as gloves, to the whole facility ³¹ .
Additional non-interventional studies
N/A
Stakeholder interviews
You become ostracized or stigmatised because you cannot follow the policy. But the policy is not appropriate for you in your setting, right? – Interview 20, Multi-outbreak international governance/policy advisor and health ethicist (Opposition; interviews mixed)
Affected communities survey

N/A	
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment	
Health benefits/harm	<p>The intervention's effectiveness is unclear, with mixed evaluations from limited evidence. Universal precautions like mask mandates may reduce stigma by avoiding targeted policies that single out specific groups. However, evidence suggests that in settings with mask mandates, stigma may shift toward those not wearing masks, especially for individuals unable to comply due to disability, environment, or cost. While some stakeholders noted that consistent policies can reduce perceived blame, others raised concerns about ostracising individuals who do not comply. Additional potential harms include undersupply of resources where they would be most effective.</p>
Uncertain	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Uncertain	
Societal implications	
Favours neither	
Human rights and acceptability	
Uncertain	
Financial and economic considerations	
Favours neither	
Feasibility of integration	<p>Universal precautions like mask mandates are relatively low-cost but may become difficult to implement universally, especially if not everyone has equal access to masks or other supplies. If ineffective in the contexts of use and resulting in insufficient supply where needed, may have negative economic consequences. Supportive measures and accessible supplies are required to ensure equitable implementation.</p>
Uncertain	
Overall quality of evidence	

Very low	Evidence from 1 observational study (GRADE Very Low) and mixed evidence from stakeholder interviews and systematic reviews of established infectious diseases (AMSTAR 2 Moderate x 1, High x 1).
----------	--

Intervention X3
Introducing low-cost reassurance measures such as temperature screening.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
N/A
Additional non-interventional studies
N/A
Stakeholder interviews
<p>"Trying to separate that from knowing that my parents work as healthcare workers at the time was a terrifying one. And I didn't feel that much stigma from school at that time. I think part of it was dealt with because Singapore was very good at taking our temperatures every morning. If they knew you had a family member who had that, I think for SARS it made sense because you there wasn't asymptomatic transmission, but that was one way of trying to deal with the fact that people who knew that my parents were health care workers, but they knew I passed my temperature check. It would have helped with that." - Interview 10, Multi-outbreak clinical responder and researcher</p> <p>" I think where it starts to get a bit tricky is when [frontline workers] want to have tests done on themselves, when they've not got any symptoms and then, you know, carry on as though everything's okay. But obviously they're dealing with their own anxieties or the anxieties of their family. And I think having an in parallel occupational health investigation of your health care workers makes sense. You know you should be getting them to check their temperature twice a day, if that's going to be a signal that you consider doing testing to pick up an asymptomatic transmission." - Interview 11, Multi-outbreak response coordinator and researcher</p> <p>"Some information around, for example, what protocols were in place to make sure that we were not posing a risk to others [was helpful for reducing stigma towards responders]. Like, for example, someone who's coming home or our volunteers are, for example, taking their temperature twice a day. And Ebola does not spread before you are symptomatic. So if you're taking your temperature twice a day and you isolate from the second that you have</p>

the beginning of an elevated temperature, you cannot pass this on to someone else. Right?"
 - Interview 16, Multi-outbreak international response coordinator and public health expert

"The effect of being a Category three returning worker is quite, don't know if it's stigmatising, but it's certainly impactful because it does make you feel like there's something wrong with you. And that suddenly you're a less favoured member of society because you're having to report in every day or you almost feel like a criminal, like you've done something wrong. And then you have to report it to your probation officer every day to say, you know, I haven't done anything wrong today. I don't have a fever. I feel well." - Interview 3, Multi-outbreak clinical responder and researcher

Affected communities survey

N/A

WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	The intervention's effectiveness is uncertain, with mixed evaluations from stakeholder interviews. Benefits include the potential to reduce stigma and alleviate public anxiety by providing visible proof of health monitoring. However, some evidence suggests that such measures can feel stigmatising or punitive, especially when rigidly enforced. The overall impact on stigma reduction and health equity will likely vary depending on how the measures are implemented and communicated.
Uncertain	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Uncertain	
Societal implications	
Uncertain	
Human rights and acceptability	Stakeholder interviews suggest mixed acceptability, with some respondents supporting temperature checks as a helpful way to reduce stigma, while others expressed concerns about the intrusiveness and feel it carries criminal connotations. The intervention's acceptability also appears to be context-dependent, with socio-cultural factors influencing perceptions of fairness and effectiveness.
Uncertain	
Financial and economic considerations	Typically low-cost and feasible but may take coordination and substantial human resources to implement. There are no data on cost-effectiveness.
Probably favours business as usual	
Feasibility of integration	
Uncertain	
Overall quality of evidence	

Very low	No direct empirical evidence from systematic review. Evidence from stakeholder interviews only.
----------	---

Intervention X4
Providing material resources or financial support to individuals recovering or to the families of the deceased.
Evidence Profile
Primary evidence from systematic review
N/A
Supporting evidence: Non-outbreak infectious disease systematic reviews
One review within Gronholm PC 2021 (AMSTAR 2: High; Pantelic et al. 2019 - AMSTAR 2: Moderate) suggested that social empowerment and economic strengthening may help reduce self-stigma ^{25,73} .
Additional non-interventional studies
In Zalwango MG 2024 (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound) public monetary and in-kind support for Ebola survivors was noted to cause further separation from community for the survivors ⁴³ . This was intended as a support measure from a number of support organisations who offered cash and household items to support the survivors and their household members. A local government official reported that, "Giving them material and monetary support in public...., the community segregates them because they assume they have more than other members." Other key informants recommended additional support needs to reduce or address stigma, including startup capital, temporary school fee support for children, and replacement of personal items (e.g., phones) destroyed during treatment.
Stakeholder interviews
"We'd have patients who we would discharge and then they would come back to us and say, Well, I'm stuck. I go home and my neighbours won't talk to me. I can't buy food at the market because nobody will take money from my hand to pay for things. I am an outcast and I don't know what to do. So I'm coming back to you. So the first ward I had, it was directly from the people who had come back to us, you know, looking for help. Since that time, we've arranged fairly systematically when people are discharged, that they are given some things to sort of smooth that over in terms of, you know, some material stuff. You know, so we don't send them home in a pair of leftover surgical scrubs or something like that, give them real clothes so that they look like a real person." - Interview 19, Viral haemorrhagic fever international response coordinator and clinical responder
Affected communities survey
Financial support for survivors and family members who lost someone to Ebola was suggested by four respondents.
WHO-INTEGRATE Assessment

Health benefits/harm	The intervention's effectiveness is uncertain, with mixed evaluations of its impact on stigma reduction and societal reintegration from one qualitative study and an indirect systematic review. Benefits include alleviating hardship and improve reintegration (important for individual benefit and health equity). However, some evidence suggests financial support may lead to further stigma, resentment, or exclusion in some settings.
Uncertain	
Health equity/non-discrimination	
Uncertain	
Societal implications	
Probably favours business as usual	
Human rights and acceptability	
Uncertain	
Financial and economic considerations	
Uncertain	
Feasibility of integration	While the intervention would require funding to implement, it may have broader financial benefits. Financial viability and feasibility are uncertain.
Uncertain	
Overall quality of evidence	Evidence from stakeholder interviews (mixed), community surveys in single context and indirect high-moderate quality systematic reviews (AMSTAR 2). Contradictory evidence from additional relevant literature (CASP: Mostly methodologically sound).
Very low	

Annex 6: Expert consultation

Methods

An expression of interest for expert consultation was distributed via ISARIC, PSI and WHO GOARN networks. A representative group of 30 experts were purposively selected to ensure balanced representation across disciplines and regions, with priority given to those who have direct experience in outbreak-related stigma reduction initiatives.

All experts pre-reviewed the draft principles and interventions as well as their associated evidence profiles and commented with additional suggestions or changes.

The expert panel also completed a survey which asked them to rate their agreement with the inclusion of each guiding principle on a 4-point likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree) given following criteria (adapted from Guyatt GH, et al. 2015⁷⁴):

- Is the message really necessary?
- Is the message clear, actionable, and achievable?
- Is the net benefit large and unequivocal?
- Is the evidence difficult to collect and summarise?
- Are there specific issues that should be considered (e.g., equity)?
- Is the rationale explicit and sound?
- Is the evidence better formally assessed?

An optional open text question asked for feedback at the end of each guiding principle. <80% agreement or strong agreement with the principle was considered the cut off to make major versus minor revisions.

All suggested changes were summarised into sets of meeting slides and each expert attended one of five three-hour expert meetings, with each focusing on in-depth review of a subset of guiding principles and recommended interventions. The expert panel tasks and consensus process for both the guiding principles and the recommended interventions are detailed below.

Expert panel tasks for guiding principles

- Pre-meeting survey: Rate agreement with principles
- Meeting task 1: Review selected principles (one domain/meeting)
- Meeting task 2: Review associated indicators
- Meeting task 3: Brief review of other domains (if time permits)
- After meeting: Finalise and approve revised principles

Consensus process for guiding principles

Expert panel tasks for recommended interventions

- *Pre-meeting review*: Provide comment on interventions and summary of evidence
- *Meeting task 1*: Review selected intervention, evidence summary, wording, notes (one phase/meeting)
- *Meeting task 2*: Determine strength of recommendation for each intervention
- *Meeting task 3*: Brief review of other phases
- *After meeting*: Finalise and approve revised interventions

Consensus process for recommended interventions

Results

We received 119 expressions of interest in the expert panel. We selected five experts from each WHO region (16 men, 13 women, 1 non-binary) with expertise across all priority pathogen groups and all outbreak response-related disciplines (**Table 8**).

Table 8: Characteristics of expert panel

Expert characteristics		No. experts (%) N=30
Gender identity	Man	16 (53)
	Woman	13 (43)
	Non-binary	1 (3)
Pathogen-specific expertise	Coronaviruses (e.g., COVID-19, MERS, SARS)	30 (100)
	Orthomyxoviruses (e.g., Influenza - all strains)	16 (53)
	Flaviviruses (e.g., Zika, Dengue, Yellow Fever)	11 (37)
	Poxviruses (e.g., Mpox)	11 (37)
	Paramyxoviruses (e.g., Nipah virus, hMPV)	11 (37)
	Cholera	9 (30)
	Filoviruses (e.g., Ebola, Marburg)	9 (30)
	Arenaviruses (e.g., Lassa fever)	3 (10)
	Bunyaviruses (e.g., Oropouche)	2 (7)
	Nairoviruses (e.g., CCHF)	2 (7)
	Corynebacterium diphtheriae (Diphtheria)	2 (7)
	Togaviruses (Chikungunya)	1 (3)
	Enteric fever	1 (3)
Roles in outbreak response	Risk communication and community engagement	22 (73)
	Social science research	16 (53)
	Personal lived experience	15 (50)
	National policy making	14 (47)
	Clinical response	11 (37)
	Patient advocacy	9 (30)
	Clinical research	9 (30)
	Psychosocial support	7 (23)
	International policy making	6 (20)
	Surveillance	2 (6)

Three selected experts were unable to participate in the expert panel activities (WHO region: Eastern Mediterranean, South East Asia, Africa; Gender: 2 men, 1 woman).

The final guiding principles and recommended interventions following expert review and consensus can be found in the main document.

Annex 7: Contributors and declarations of interest

On review of all affiliations and declarations of interest, no conflicts of interest were identified. All guideline contributors are listed below.

Table 9: Guideline contributors and declarations of interest

Name	Declarations of interest
Amy Paterson	None to declare
Chambrez-Zita Zauchenberger	None to declare
Mary Gouws	None to declare
Ruan Spies	None to declare
Amanda Rojek	None to declare
Ashleigh Cheyne	None to declare
Piero Olliaro	None to declare
Nina Gobat	None to declare
Anne Stangl	First author of a systematic review on stigma reduction in established infectious disease contexts considered as indirect evidence in the development of this work.
Antons Mozalevskis	None to declare
Eka Airlangga	None to declare
Hager Saeed	None to declare
Harun Tulunay	Trustee of Plushealth and Sexpression; Steering group member of UK-CAB; Patient representative on NHS England HIV CRG Board.
Ismat Jahan Bhuiyan	None to declare
Jeni Stolow	None to declare
Jennifer Collins	None to declare
John Robert Carabeo Medina	None to declare
Kkunsu Hadson Dimitrios	None to declare

Laura De Almeida	None to declare
Maria Bertoglia	None to declare
Markita Suttle	None to declare
Md Saiful Islam	None to declare
Mumtaz Ali Khan	None to declare
Naveed Ahmed	None to declare
Nicole Martin	None to declare
Parth Sharma	None to declare
Petra Gronholm	First author of a systematic review on stigma reduction in established infectious disease contexts considered as indirect evidence in the development of this work.
Rayner Kay Jin Tan	None to declare
Rihab Yazidi	None to declare
Samuel Tomczyk	None to declare
Shreyus Sukhija	None to declare
Toru Takenaga	None to declare
Ursin Bayisenge	None to declare
Zeb Jamrozik	None to declare
Olive Kabajaasi	None to declare
Nathan Kenya-Mugisha	None to declare
Tonmoy Sarkar	None to declare
Syed Satter	None to declare

References

1. Paterson, A., Spies, R., Zauchenberger, C.-Z. & Rojek, A. Effectiveness of Stigma Reduction Interventions and Outbreak Response Adaptations in Infectious Disease Outbreaks: A Systematic Review. *PROSPERO* (2025).
2. Cicchetti, D. V. & Sparrow, S. A. Developing criteria for establishing interrater reliability of specific items: applications to assessment of adaptive behavior. *Am J Ment Defic* **86**, 127–137 (1981).
3. Cochrane Methods Bias. RoB 2: A revised Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials. <https://methods.cochrane.org/bias/resources/rob-2-revised-cochrane-risk-bias-tool-randomized-trials> (2019).
4. Cochrane Methods Bias. ROBINS-I. <https://methods.cochrane.org/bias/risk-bias-non-randomized-studies-interventions> (2024).
5. CASP. Qualitative Studies Checklist - CASP. *CASP - Critical Appraisal Skills Programme* <https://casp-uk.net/casp-tools-checklists/qualitative-studies-checklist/> (2024).
6. GRADE. GRADE handbook. <https://gdt.gradepro.org/app/handbook/handbook.html#h.ged5uqebmir9> (2013).
7. GRADE CERQual. GRADE-CERQual. <https://www.cerqual.org/> (2018).
8. Biesty, C. P. *et al.* Community led health promotion to counter stigma and increase trust amongst priority populations: lessons from the 2022–2023 UK mpox outbreak. *BMC Public Health* **24**, 1638 (2024).
9. Collier, K. M. *et al.* Ebola Virus Disease Sensitization: Community-Driven Efforts in Sierra Leone. *J Community Health* **49**, 108–116 (2024).

10. Crea, T. M. *et al.* Social distancing, community stigma, and implications for psychological distress in the aftermath of Ebola virus disease. *PLoS One* **17**, e0276790 (2022).
11. Islam, A., Pakrashi, D., Vlassopoulos, M. & Wang, L. C. Stigma and Misconceptions in the Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Field Experiment in India. (2020).
12. Lu, T. *et al.* Effects of Wise Intervention on Perceived Discrimination Among College Students Returning Home From Wuhan During the COVID-19 Outbreak. *Front Psychol* **12**, 689251 (2021).
13. Siu, J. Y. The SARS-associated stigma of SARS victims in the post-SARS era of Hong Kong. *Qual Health Res* **18**, 729–738 (2008).
14. Smith, R. A. An Experimental Test of Stigma Communication Content with a Hypothetical Infectious Disease Alert. *Communication Monographs* **79**, 522–538 (2012).
15. Techapoonpon, K., Wonglertwisawakorn, C., Kerdchareon, N., Pruttithavorn, W. & Sriksamdokkhae, O. Can a brief session of the online coronavirus disease 2019 destigmatization program reduce stigma among survivors? A randomized controlled trial. *Front Psychiatry* **14**, 1234038 (2023).
16. Tidwell, J. B. *et al.* The limits of nudging: Results of a randomized trial of text messages to promote home-based caregiving and reduce perceptions of stigma for COVID-19 patients in Kenyan informal settlements. *PLoS One* **19**, e0305206 (2024).
17. Valeri, L., Amsalem, D., Jankowski, S., Susser, E. & Dixon, L. Effectiveness of a Video-Based Intervention on Reducing Perceptions of Fear, Loneliness, and

- Public Stigma Related to COVID-19: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Int J Public Health* **66**, 1604164 (2021).
18. Wang, Y., Zhu, J., Wang, J. & Mu, Y. Oxytocin modulation of explicit pandemic stigma in men with varying social anxiety levels. *Neuropharmacology* **261**, 110140 (2024).
19. Shea, B. J. *et al.* AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both. *BMJ* **358**, j4008 (2017).
20. Anindhita, M. *et al.* Community-based psychosocial support interventions to reduce stigma and improve mental health of people with infectious diseases: a scoping review. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty* **13**, 90 (2024).
21. Chang, S.-H. & Cataldo, J. K. A systematic review of global cultural variations in knowledge, attitudes and health responses to tuberculosis stigma. *The International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease* **18**, 168–173 (2014).
22. Driedger, M. *et al.* Accessibility and Acceptability of Infectious Disease Interventions Among Migrants in the EU/EEA: A CERQual Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* **15**, 2329 (2018).
23. Feyissa, G. T., Lockwood, C. & Munn, Z. The effectiveness of home-based HIV counseling and testing on reducing stigma and risky sexual behavior among adults and adolescents: A systematic review and meta-analyses. *JBI Database System Rev Implement Rep* **13**, 318–372 (2015).

24. Gronholm, P. C. *et al.* Reducing stigma and discrimination associated with COVID-19: early stage pandemic rapid review and practical recommendations. *Epidemiol Psychiatr Sci* **30**, e15 (2021).
25. Hartog, K. *et al.* Stigma reduction interventions for children and adolescents in low- and middle-income countries: Systematic review of intervention strategies. *Social Science & Medicine* **246**, 112749 (2020).
26. Hofstraat, K. & van Brakel, W. H. Social stigma towards neglected tropical diseases: a systematic review. *Int Health* **8 Suppl 1**, i53-70 (2016).
27. Kemp, C. G. *et al.* Implementation science and stigma reduction interventions in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *BMC Medicine* **17**, 6 (2019).
28. Layland, E. K. *et al.* A systematic review of stigma in sexual and gender minority health interventions. *Transl Behav Med* **10**, 1200–1210 (2020).
29. Majeed, T. *et al.* Anti-stigma interventions in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *eClinicalMedicine* **72**, (2024).
30. Nyblade, L. *et al.* Stigma in health facilities: why it matters and how we can change it. *BMC Medicine* **17**, 25 (2019).
31. Rao, D. *et al.* A systematic review of multi-level stigma interventions: state of the science and future directions. *BMC Medicine* **17**, 41 (2019).
32. Sengupta, S., Banks, B., Jonas, D., Miles, M. S. & Smith, G. C. HIV interventions to reduce HIV/AIDS stigma: a systematic review. *AIDS Behav* **15**, 1075–1087 (2011).

33. Stangl, A. L., Lloyd, J. K., Brady, L. M., Holland, C. E. & Baral, S. A systematic review of interventions to reduce HIV-related stigma and discrimination from 2002 to 2013: how far have we come? *J Int AIDS Soc* **16**, 18734 (2013).
34. Stangl, A. L. *et al.* What do we know about interventions to reduce intersectional stigma and discrimination in the context of HIV? A systematic review. *Stigma and Health* **8**, 393–408 (2023).
35. Fargnoli, V., Nehme, M., Guessous, I. & Burton-Jeangros, C. Acceptability of COVID-19 Certificates: A Qualitative Study in Geneva, Switzerland, in 2020. *Front. Public Health* **9**, (2021).
36. Ford, C. L. *et al.* Adequacy of Existing Surveillance Systems to Monitor Racism, Social Stigma and COVID Inequities: A Detailed Assessment and Recommendations. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* **18**, 13099 (2021).
37. Kwon, P., Soyoung. Mask Wearing and Perceived Discrimination Associated With COVID-19 in the United States From March 2020 to May 2021: Three-Level Longitudinal Analyses. *Health Educ Behav* **49**, 200–209 (2022).
38. Lamb, D. Factors affecting the delivery of healthcare on a humanitarian operation in West Africa: A qualitative study. *Applied Nursing Research* **40**, 129–136 (2018).
39. Musoke, D. *et al.* Barriers to community engagement during the response to an Ebola virus disease outbreak in Uganda. *BMJ Glob Health* **10**, e017285 (2025).
40. Nyarko, Y., Goldfrank, L., Ogedegbe, G., Soghoian, S. & de-Graft Aikins, A. Preparing for Ebola Virus Disease in West African countries not yet affected: perspectives from Ghanaian health professionals. *Global Health* **11**, 7 (2015).

41. Parveen, S. *et al.* It's not only what you say, it's also how you say it: communicating Nipah virus prevention messages during an outbreak in Bangladesh. *BMC Public Health* **16**, 726 (2016).
42. Person, B. *et al.* Fear and Stigma: The Epidemic within the SARS Outbreak. *Emerg Infect Dis* **10**, 358–363 (2004).
43. Zalwango, M. G. *et al.* Stigma among ebola disease survivors in Mubende and Kassanda districts, Central Uganda, 2022. *PLOS Glob Public Health* **4**, e0003272 (2024).
44. Paterson, A. *et al.* An hourglass model for conceptualising stigma in infectious disease outbreaks. *Sci Rep* **15**, 15339 (2025).
45. Rehfuess, E. A. *et al.* The WHO-INTEGRATE evidence to decision framework version 1.0: integrating WHO norms and values and a complexity perspective. *BMJ Glob Health* **4**, (2019).
46. Krameddine, Y., DeMarco, D., Hassel, R. & Silverstone, P. H. A Novel Training Program for Police Officers that Improves Interactions with Mentally Ill Individuals and is Cost-Effective. *Front. Psychiatry* **4**, (2013).
47. Hanisch, S. E. *et al.* The effectiveness of interventions targeting the stigma of mental illness at the workplace: a systematic review. *BMC Psychiatry* **16**, 1 (2016).
48. Shah, S. M., Heylen, E., Srinivasan, K., Perumpil, S. & Ekstrand, M. L. Reducing HIV Stigma Among Nursing Students: A Brief Intervention. *West J Nurs Res* **36**, 1323–1337 (2014).

49. el-Setouhy, M. A. & Rio, F. Stigma reduction and improved knowledge and attitudes towards filariasis using a comic book for children. *J Egypt Soc Parasitol* **33**, 55–65 (2003).
50. Denison, J. A. *et al.* Do peer educators make a difference? An evaluation of a youth-led HIV prevention model in Zambian Schools. *Health Educ Res* **27**, 237–247 (2012).
51. Al-Iryani, B., Basaleem, H., Al-Sakkaf, K., Kok, G. & van den Borne, B. Process evaluation of school-based peer education for HIV prevention among Yemeni adolescents. *SAHARA J* **10**, 55–64 (2013).
52. Tora, A., Tadele, G., Aseffa, A., McBride, C. M. & Davey, G. Health beliefs of school-age rural children in podoconiosis-affected families: A qualitative study in Southern Ethiopia. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* **11**, e0005564 (2017).
53. Wilson, J. W., Ramos, J. G., Castillo, F., F. Castellanos, E. & Escalante, P. Tuberculosis patient and family education through videography in El Salvador. *Journal of Clinical Tuberculosis and Other Mycobacterial Diseases* **4**, 14–20 (2016).
54. Rice, R. E., Wu, Z., Li, L., Detels, R. & Rotheram-Borus, M. J. Reducing STD/HIV Stigmatizing Attitudes Through Community Popular Opinion Leaders in Chinese Markets. *Hum Commun Res* **38**, 379–405 (2012).
55. Stangl, A. L. *et al.* What do we know about interventions to reduce intersectional stigma and discrimination in the context of HIV? A systematic review. *Stigma and Health* **8**, 393–408 (2023).

56. Peters, R. M. H. *et al.* A Cluster-Randomized Controlled Intervention Study to Assess the Effect of a Contact Intervention in Reducing Leprosy-Related Stigma in Indonesia. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases* **9**, e0004003 (2015).
57. Zeelen, J., Wijbenga, H., Vintges, M. & de Jong, G. Beyond silence and rumor: Storytelling as an educational tool to reduce the stigma around HIV/AIDS in South Africa. *Health Education* **110**, 382–398 (2010).
58. Mak, W. W. S., Cheng, S. S. Y., Law, R. W., Cheng, W. W. L. & Chan, F. Reducing HIV-related stigma among health-care professionals: a game-based experiential approach. *AIDS Care* **27**, 855–859 (2015).
59. Winkler, P. *et al.* Short video interventions to reduce mental health stigma: a multi-centre randomised controlled trial in nursing high schools. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol* **52**, 1549–1557 (2017).
60. Clarke, S., Taylor, G., Bolderston, H., Lancaster, J. & Remington, B. Ameliorating Patient Stigma Amongst Staff Working With Personality Disorder: Randomized Controlled Trial of Self-Management Versus Skills Training. *Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy* **43**, 692–704 (2015).
61. Lusli, M. *et al.* Lay and peer counsellors to reduce leprosy-related stigma – lessons learnt in Cirebon, Indonesia. *Leprosy Review* **86**, 37–53 (2015).
62. Watt, M. H. *et al.* Acceptability of a group intervention for initiates of antiretroviral therapy in Tanzania. *Global Public Health* **6**, 433–446 (2011).
63. Salmen, C. R. *et al.* “Wan Kanyakla” (We are together): Community transformations in Kenya following a social network intervention for HIV care. *Social Science & Medicine* **147**, 332–340 (2015).

64. Norr, K. F., Norr, J. L., McElmurry, B. J., Tlou, S. & Moeti, M. R. Impact of peer group education on HIV prevention among women in Botswana. *Health Care Women Int* **25**, 210–226 (2004).
65. Gurnani, V. *et al.* An integrated structural intervention to reduce vulnerability to HIV and sexually transmitted infections among female sex workers in Karnataka state, south India. *BMC Public Health* **11**, 755 (2011).
66. Dickens, B. L., Koo, J. R., Wilder-Smith, A. & Cook, A. R. Institutional, not home-based, isolation could contain the COVID-19 outbreak. *The Lancet* **395**, 1541–1542 (2020).
67. Zhu, P. & Tan, X. Is compulsory home quarantine less effective than centralized quarantine in controlling the COVID-19 outbreak? Evidence from Hong Kong. *Sustainable Cities and Society* **74**, 103222 (2021).
68. Reagu, S. *et al.* Psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic within institutional quarantine and isolation centres and its sociodemographic correlates in Qatar: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open* **11**, e045794 (2021).
69. Ndejjo, R., Naggayi, G., Tibiita, R., Mugahi, R. & Kibira, S. P. S. Experiences of persons in COVID-19 institutional quarantine in Uganda: a qualitative study. *BMC Public Health* **21**, 482 (2021).
70. Sopory, P., Novak, J. M. & Noyes, J. P. Quarantine acceptance and adherence: qualitative evidence synthesis and conceptual framework. *J Public Health (Berl.)* **30**, 2091–2101 (2022).
71. Chu, I. Y.-H., Alam, P., Larson, H. J. & Lin, L. Social consequences of mass quarantine during epidemics: a systematic review with implications for the COVID-19 response. *J Travel Med* **27**, taaa192 (2020).

72. Chen, D. *et al.* Quarantine experience of close contacts of COVID-19 patients in China: A qualitative descriptive study. *Gen Hosp Psychiatry* **66**, 81–88 (2020).
73. Pantelic, M., Steinert, J. I., Park, J., Mellors, S. & Murau, F. 'Management of a spoiled identity': systematic review of interventions to address self-stigma among people living with and affected by HIV. *BMJ Glob Health* **4**, e001285 (2019).
74. Guyatt, G. H., Schünemann, H. J., Djulbegovic, B. & Akl, E. A. Guideline panels should not GRADE good practice statements. *J Clin Epidemiol* **68**, 597–600 (2015).